

[D2.2] REPORT ON SUPPLY CHAIN STRATEGIES FOR RESILIENCE AND SUSTAINABILITY

Project details

Project Title	Reshaping Supply Chains for Positive Social Impact
Project Type:	RIA
Project Acronym	ReSChape
Grant Agreement No.	101061729
Duration	36 Months
Project Start Date	October 1, 2022

Document details

WP:	2	WP Leader:	CNR
WP Title:	Global trends and Innovative supply chain models		
Deliverable No.	D2.2		
Deliverable Title	Report on supply chain strategies for resilience and sustainability		
Dissemination level	Public report		
Responsible partner	INESC TEC		
Contributing beneficiaries	CNR, ASTON, Fraunhofer IML, ZLC, RWI and DEUSTO		
Approved by	CNR		
Status	Version 0.1-00		
Date	18/10/2023		

Deliverable information

Status (F: final; D: draft; RD: revised draft):	D
Planned delivery date	30/09/2023
Actual delivery date	18/10/2023
Dissemination level: (PU = Public; PP = Restricted to other program participants; RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium; CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium)	PU
Type: Report, Website, Other, Ethics	Report

Quality check review

Reviewer (s)	Main changes
CNR	Change the position of some sections, propose some content, improve executive summary and conclusions.

Document history

Version	Date	Remarks
0.1	01/09/2023	Table of content
0.2	29/09/2023	First draft released by INESC TEC
0.3	02/10/2023	Revision from CNR
0.4	09/10/2023	New draft released by INESC TEC
0.5	11/10/2023	New comments from CNR
1.0	17/10/2023	Final version and submission to EC

Table of contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. INTRODUCTION	6
2. CONTEXT AND MAIN DEFINITIONS	8
3. METHODOLOGY AND MODEL DEVELOPMENT	12
Identification of risks	13
Identification and classification of actions	13
Model development	15
Validation Workshop	18
4. RESULTS	20
Actions for supply chain sustainability and resilience.....	20
Model: Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar.....	30
Using the Model	31
1. CONCLUSIONS	35
REFERENCES	37
Appendix 1 – List of papers on supply chain sustainability and resilience.....	56

List of abbreviations and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
EC	European Commission
HR	Human resources
IoT	Internet of Things
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal, Environmental
SC	Supply Chain
SCM	Supply Chain Management
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SME	Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprise

Disclaimer

This deliverable may be subject to final acceptance by the European Commission. The results of these deliverables reflect only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Statement for open documents & Copyrights.

This document is property of the ReSChape Consortium. The content of all or parts of these documents can be used and distributed provided that the ReSChape project and the document are properly referenced.

INESC TEC and the ReSChape consortium are keen on ensuring that all information in this document is correct and fairly stated but does not accept liability for any errors or omissions.

At the best of our knowledge, all third-party literary (articles/studies/reports/etc. or excerpts thereof) or artistic (photos/graphs/drawings/etc.) used to support this document are correctly cited and acknowledged. If the reader should find something not compliant, an additional courtesy acknowledgement or correction can be made to this version thereof.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the results of the task T2.3 “Definition of SC strategies for resilience and sustainability”. This task aimed to identify strategies to be applied by companies and supply chains in order to increase their social, environmental and economic sustainability as well as their capacity to be ready, to respond and to recover from unexpected events. Considering the challenges that characterize the current supply chain environments, this task investigates how supply chains can deal simultaneously with both aspects, sustainability and resilience.

The work started from the results of the T2.2 where risks for supply chains have been identified and prioritised based on trends and megatrends of PESTLE dimensions. In order to support the definition of strategies, the first step was the identification of actions that can be adopted as responses to those risks, considering that they represent the most prominent issues of current and future supply chain environments. A systematic approach was applied to search for previous works to identify ways to tackle risks. The literature review intended to identify: (1) studies that suggest supply chain models and strategies to address sustainability and resilience aspects; and (2) studies that focus on specific actions for supply chain risks. More than 100 actions emerged from this comprehensive work covering a wide range of topics such as new devices for worker safety, implementation of platforms for worker training, new configuration of supply chain processes, and new monitoring systems covering different processes of supply chain.

As a further step in the task, using a content analysis approach, the actions were clustered according to their main contribution to each of the three sustainability dimensions and to different resilience capabilities, giving rise to a set of different strategies. The innovative model developed in this task, namely the “Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar”, allows supply chain actors to explore the actions in different ways in order to identify the most appropriate strategy for each specific context. Besides sustainability dimensions and resilience capabilities, the actions can be “filtered” according to their level of prioritization (resulting from the probability and severity of their related risks) and the PESTLE analysis dimension to which they are most connected to. The results can be used by managers as a guide to deal with the complexity and uncertainty of supply chains, especially in the European context.

The model is designed to be dynamic, both in terms of its application and its evolution. Concerning the application, each company, starting from its own challenges, can identify actions which can fit with its own request. As for the evolution, the model is a “living tool” because new actions can be incorporated when appropriate, and current actions can be excluded if the probability and impact of the related risk are considered to decrease substantially.

1. INTRODUCTION

The contemporary context is characterized by successive, increasingly frequent, and far-reaching events, with a major impact on people's lives. Some of them are hard-to-predict crises – the so-called black swan events – such as the COVID 19 pandemic, the war in Ukraine and the Brexit. Other events are the result of actions taken over time that undermined different aspects of society and the environment, such as the overpopulation in certain parts of the globe, the refugees' crises, the scarcity of water, among others (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Context - Contemporary challenges

At the same time, companies and supply chains face several business challenges, many of them related to the predominant model of global supply chains. As an example, a simple dress can travel around the globe before reaching the final consumer (could be virtually any supply chain), with consequences to the sustainability and the resilience of supply chains. The changes into business models caused by modified consumer behaviour, such as the use of batteries for powering mobile electronics and their manufacturing process affecting the working conditions at Congo's cobalt mines, are other examples regarding the problems currently faced by supply chains that intended to become more sustainable and resilient. Figure 2 represents some of these challenges.

These phenomena and multiplicity of future developments regarding different topics were extensively examined in the tasks 2.1 and 2.2 of this project. They were referred to as megatrends – large, slow-forming socio-economic, political, environmental, or technological changes that are particularly useful for forecasting the future of manufacturing, process manufacturing, logistics, and supply chain management – and subsequently divided into trends, which helps to give a direction of movement, development, or change and build more specific subgroups of the overarching megatrends. Additionally, the supporting work for this research has also categorized the megatrends and trends according to the six PESTLE dimensions – Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental – so that the future supply chain scenarios were observed from complementary points of view, leading to the identification of risks for each of these dimensions, representing events that disrupt or impede the information, material or product flows from original suppliers to the delivery of the final product to the ultimate end-user. The set of risks were, hence, used as a starting ground for the understanding of the interactions between sustainability dimensions

and resilience capabilities, paving the ground towards the development and establishment of sustainable and resilient supply chain strategies.

Figure 1: Context - business and supply chain challenges

Many contemporary challenges represented by the megatrends and trends related to political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental aspects and several business risks that increase the complexity and the uncertainties of supply chains, impacting their resilience and sustainability, were evaluated. Considering this context, it is very difficult to overlook resilience and sustainability as priorities when it comes to supply chain management. For instance, a company cannot choose to deal with sustainability during the next two years and after that, tackle resilience issues. Both are urgent and must be faced at the same time (Ivanov, 2018; Silva et al., 2023). On the one hand, megatrends and trends represent a macro perspective whose effects are observed in all aspects of society. On the other hand, business management and supply chain risks arising from megatrends and trends, such as the advent of global supply chains, new consumption habits, the paradigm of digital transformation and multiple humanitarian needs present themselves as a micro perspective that impacts the way companies interact with their partners both upstream and downstream. Hence, the increased complexity and uncertainty of these macro and micro approaches require a joint effort in terms of supply chain management strategies that tackle both the sustainability dimensions and the resilience capabilities, as portrayed in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Overall approach to dealing with complexity and uncertainty in supply chain management

Thus, the goal of this task was to identify approaches that businesses and their supply chain partners may use to improve their social, environmental, and economic sustainability as well as their ability to prepare for, respond to, and recover from unforeseen events. This task assumes that businesses must create measures that address both sustainability and resilience simultaneously in light of the difficulties that currently exist in supply chain systems.

2. CONTEXT AND MAIN DEFINITIONS

Sustainability is often defined as the development that assures the present needs without harming future generations to meet their own needs (European Commission, 2022; Elkington J, 1994) and encompasses three dimensions that must be managed complementarily and support each other: environmental, social and economic. Although sustainability has been broadly discussed during the last few decades, the concepts around the term have increased in complexity as the complexity of social and business contexts increases as well. The European Commission (2022) highlights that economic development must be aligned with social justice, respect for human rights, high labour standards and high environmental standards to promote sustainable development. Current supply chain management approaches to sustainability issues include practices such as green supply chains, closed-loop supply chains, circular supply chains, social justice in supply chains, and humanitarian supply chains, among others.

Previous studies on supply chain sustainability generally agree that adopting sustainable practices ensures business continuity while lowering long-term risks. Business continuity is also one of the essential elements of a resilient supply chain (Ivanov, 2018). However, although recent studies have recognized that sustainability and resilience should be considered part of the same efforts in the context of a transformative perspective (Silva et al., 2023), research combining both constructs is just beginning (Ivanov, 2018).

Thus, in order to identify the current knowledge on the relationship between resilience and sustainability in the supply chain management literature, a literature review using a systematic approach was performed. The systematic method suggested by Denyer and Tranfield (2009) was used to ensure that the review is transparent, auditable and replicable. A systematic literature review consists of the identification, selection, analysis and synthesis of existing research on a particular topic and its presentation in a clear manner in order to meet what is known and not known about the topic – as depicted in Figure 4 (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). This deliverable uses the following steps proposed by Denyer and Tranfield (2009): (1) location of studies; (2) selection and evaluation of studies; (3) analysis and synthesis; (4) presentation of results.

Figure 3: Steps carried out for the review of the literature (Source: adapted from Denyer & Tranfield, 2009)

The first step was the location of relevant studies. Words related to resilience, sustainability and supply chain were used to search for previous studies. Following recent studies, Scopus was defined as the database for the search, which was based on all possible combinations of the three groups of keywords. Only journals (articles and reviews) were searched, limited to the areas of “Business Economics”, “Engineering”, “Operations Research Management Science”, “Environmental Sciences”, “Social Sciences” and “Decision Sciences”. There was no restriction for the date of

publication. The first search, carried out on May 31, 2023, returned a total of 870 items. The following search string was used:

```
( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "resilien*" AND "sustainab*" ) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "supply chain" OR "value chain" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "English" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) )
```

After the abstract reading, 104 papers that were related to the objectives of the research were maintained and were fully read by the researchers. After the final reading, 59 papers were selected as the final sample (the full list of papers can be found in Appendix 1).

Figure 5 presents the years when the papers have been published. The analysis shows that the number of papers that address sustainability and resilience of supply chains simultaneously has been increasing in the last two years. Only the years 2022 and 2023 (until May) represent almost 60% of the articles identified, showing the topicality of the theme.

Figure 4: Number of papers per year (*until May)

The papers were published in 31 different Journals (Figure 6), demonstrating the broad interest on the topic. Journals covering different scientific areas have papers included in the final samples, although the journals more related to sustainability issues are the ones with the higher number of papers.

Figure 5: Publication sources

A qualitative analysis of the papers allowed a deeper understanding on the topics under study and provided insights on types of activities to be carried out by supply chains towards sustainability and resilience. Sazvar et al. (2021), for example, analyse the vaccine supply chains and highlight the importance of sustainability actions related to product responsibility, labour rights, job creation, social anxiety, deprivation and pollution, while addressing criticality, complexity, density, redundancy and failure as the main resilience concerns. Mahrjerdi and Shafiee (2021) explore the relationship between a set of supply chain features related to resilience (availability, complexity, performance loss, SC robustness, differentiation, visibility, customer service level, technical resource restoration, percentage of unfulfilled demand post-disaster) on the three sustainability dimensions. Negri et al. (2022) provide a list of sustainability practices divided into twelve categories (internal environmental management, green purchasing, cooperation with customers, ecodesign, investment recovery, environmental innovation, environmental performance, green compliance, green marketing, suppliers relationship, logistics and social practices) and a list of resilience practices, also divided in proactive actions (related to risk management, flexibility, reserve capacity, integration and collaboration, efficiency, market and financial strength, node density, complexity and criticality), response and agility).

However, the analysis demonstrated the need to further discuss and create practical models that can be applied by companies. The analysis shows that, although referring to sustainability and resilience, several papers address mainly one of the two aspects, considering the second as a minor concern or a consequence, suggesting the need to develop models that address both aspects in a balanced and comprehensive way. Costa et al. (2022), for instance, evaluate the impact of resilience practices on food waste. Pu et al. (2023) analyses sustainable competitive advantage as a consequence of supply chain resilience.

Moreover, some papers address only one sustainability dimension. Ji et al. (2020), for instance, study the role of proactive and reactive resilience actions on the development of green supply chains, while Singh et al (2018) focus on humanitarian supply chains. On the other hand, some authors use a limiting definition of supply chain resilience. The concept of resilience is interdisciplinary and was first coined as the capacity of a system to adapt to change (Holling, 1973). Since then, numerous authors have reiterated the idea of resilience as a system's capacity to recover and go back to its initial state. In this work, resilience is understood as the capacity to persist, adapt or transform in the face of change (Wieland & Durach, 2021), which means that being resilient does not necessarily

imply returning to the initial state. Finding new ways to deal with the market needs (by means of adaptation or transformation) is also considered resilience.

It is commonly considered that the resilience "process" encompasses three moments: readiness, response and recovery. Readiness is related to preparing the supply chain in order to decrease its exposure to disruptive events, implying the capabilities to identify and mitigate/avoid risks before damage happens. Response is related to how quickly and efficiently a company acts during urgent situations, while recovery is associated with the post-event and the capacity to recuperate from that (Sheffi et. al 2005; Chowdhury & Quaddus, 2016). Thus, the actions to increase supply chain resilience can be divided into proactive actions, closely related to the concept of readiness, and reactive actions, linked to the capabilities to respond and recover (Chowdhury et. al 2017; Rahman et al., 2022).

Adapting the model presented by Chowdhury et al. (2017), this study seeks to predominantly identify proactive actions, considering that these actions allow supply chain actors greater control over their operations, even in times of crisis and, therefore, have a greater possibility of contributing to companies persisting, adapting or transforming according to the scenario. Reactive actions are also identified and contribute to faster response and recovery in the face of unexpected events. Proactive capabilities can be further divided into flexibility, redundancy, integration/visibility, efficiency, market strength, financial strength and readiness. In general terms, flexibility can be understood as the ability to change according to a given situation. In terms of supply chain resilience, flexibility can represent being able to change production patterns (e.g., quantity, scheduling, inputs), sourcing or distribution routines (e.g., new suppliers, substitute components, new routes and transport modes), as well, as developing customization capacity and developing a multi-skilled workforce. Redundancy means having reserve capacity (in terms of production and distribution), stock (of raw material, components or products) and back-up utilities to use them if necessary (as a plan B). Integration and visibility represent the ability to connect systems and procedures as well as the capacity to have access to and/or to provide the required timely information from and to relevant partners for better decision support (Messina et al., 2022), encompassing collaboration and information sharing. Reducing waste, increasing the productivity and effectiveness of the workforce and ensuring an adequate quality control are ways to enhance efficiency, and robustness as a consequence. Strengthening the companies' position in terms of market (e.g., satisfaction, brand image, differentiation, relationship with customers) and finance (e.g., diversification, funding availability, profit consistency and insurance) are also ways to boost resilience. Table 1 presents examples of types of action to each resilience capability.

Table 1 – Resilience capabilities (Source: adapted from Chowdhury et. al 2017)

Resilience capability		Examples of types of actions
Proactive	Flexibility	Production flexibility
		customization
		Multi-skilled workforce
		Contract flexibility
		Sourcing flexibility
		Distribution flexibility
	Redundancy	Reserve capacity
		stock
		Back-up utilities
	Integration/visibility	Information sharing

Resilience capability		Examples of types of actions
		Internal integration
		collaboration
		ICT adoption
	Efficiency	Waste reduction
		Efficiency of employees
		Quality control
	Market strength	Buyer-supplier satisfaction
		Preferred brand
		Buyer-supplier relation
		Product differentiation
	Financial strength	diversified business portfolio
		Fund availability
		Profit consistency
		Insurance
	Readiness	Disruption detection
		Readiness training
		Readiness resource
Early warning signal		
Forecasting		
Security		
Reactive	Response	Quick response
		Adequate response
		Response team
	Recovery	Quick recovery
		Loss absorption
		Reduction of impact
		Recovery cost

Thus, this work intends to apply a comprehensive view of the two aspects, sustainability and resilience, and ensure that they are addressed in a balanced way in order to contribute to practice, by providing a broad list of actions that can be explored in different perspectives, and to theory, by filling current gaps identified in the literature.

3. METHODOLOGY AND MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The methodology adopted in task 2.3 encompasses four main steps with the main goal of identifying actions and developing strategies to sustainable and resilient supply chains, as represented in Figure 9.

Figure 6: Detailed components and research methodology

IDENTIFICATION OF RISKS

The initial stage of the research began by utilizing the results from the previous task (T2.2), where an identification of risks for SCs based on the PESTLE framework was conducted. During this stage, risks related to trends and megatrends in the context of supply chains were identified, validated, and classified with regards to the three sustainability dimensions – Economic, Social and Environment – which was achieved through an extensive literature review. Additionally, resulting risks were validated through a workshop with experts, where the definition of impact and probability of occurrence of each risk was determined, as well as the discussion of potential unforeseen and unidentified risks. A preliminary discussion of possible actions to either mitigate, avoid or attenuate the risks was also performed with the experts during this workshop. Figure 10 presents an overview of the methodology used to identify risks in Task 2.2.

Figure 7: Identification of the risks in T2.2

IDENTIFICATION AND CLASSIFICATION OF ACTIONS

The identification of actions to enable sustainable and resilient supply chains considered the results of two steps. In the first step, the papers analysed for the identification of risks in T2.2 were further reviewed to collect, if present, actions to avoid, mitigate, or accept the encountered risks.

In the second step another search has been carried out within the Scopus database in order to identify supplementary literature specifically for the actions. The timeframe used considered more recent papers published in high-ranking journals from 2020 onwards. The following “modular” search string was used for this purpose through a set of customised strings:

```
( TITLE-ABS-KEY (“risk keyword”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "supply chain" OR "value chain" ) )  
AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "English" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) )
```

When risks were too specific and it was not possible to find papers to identify actions, keywords related to the “megatrend” OR “trend” – as identified in a previous stage of this research – were used instead of “risk keyword”. Below there are two examples of search strings used in this step.

Megatrend – Protectionism; Risk – Price variation

```
( TITLE-ABS-KEY (“price variation”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "supply chain" OR "value chain" ) )  
AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "English" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE , "ar" ) )
```

Megatrend – Digital economy; Risk – Poor infrastructure and low capital

```
( TITLE-ABS-KEY (“poor infrastructure” OR “low capital”) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( "supply chain"  
OR "value chain" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( LANGUAGE , "English" ) ) AND ( LIMIT-TO ( DOCTYPE  
, "ar" ) )  
term”.
```

After the identification stage, actions were classified according to:

- Responsible actor for the action (supply chain actors and/or policy makers). These 2 categories of actors are useful to split the actions to be studied in WP2 and WP3 (related to supply chain actors) and in WP4 (related to policy makers);
- Resilience capabilities according to the definition of Chowdhury et al. (2017), as explained in Section 2;
- Sustainability dimensions resulting from T2.2: Economic, Social and Environment;
- Actions prioritization stemming from the risk prioritization resulted from T2.2 - Very High, High, Medium, Low or Very Low in terms of probability and expected impact on the SCs.

As shown on Figure 11 below, the identified actions and their classification have been collected in a shared electronic spreadsheet with the support of the consortium partners. Harmonization and clustering of the actions was performed by the Task Leader with aid from Consortium partners in order to depict the actions from sustainability dimensions and resilience capabilities.

Megatrend	Risks	Prioritization	Actions	Responsible	Resilience	Sustainability	References
Increasing amount of data	1. Safety of personal/confidential data					Social	
	2. Lack or high demanding (current or future) regulatory frameworks					Economic	
	3. Poor data analysis and decision-making					Economic	
	4. Lack of shared data standards.					Economic	
	5. Low data visibility due to poor adoption of technology					Economic	
	6. High investment for the analysis and storage of data					Economic	
	7. High energy consumption due to storage and processing needs					Environmental	

Pre-filled fields

Fields to be filled

Figure 8: Example of the electronic spreadsheet used to support the identification of actions

After this, a workshop with experts was promoted to validate not only the formulated actions but also to discuss the classification given in terms of sustainability and resilience. During the workshop, it was also possible to add new actions and suggest synergies and trade-offs between them. The result of this comprehensive work was the identification of more than 100 actions that cover a broad range of aspects.

An ID was defined to the actions from the PESTLE dimension of the risk and a sequential number (e.g., P_1 – Political; E_1 – Economic; S_1 – Social, T_1 – Technological; L_1 – Legal; and EN_1 – Enviromental).

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

As emerged from the analysis of the literature (section 2), sustainability and resilience have to be treated by supply chain actors as priorities that must be addressed simultaneously. With this purpose, the consortium has conceived a model to support the definition of strategies through the aggregation of elements of sustainability and resilience in a single and integrative view.

Firstly, the actions were grouped into the sustainability dimensions, using a content analysis approach and according to the classification given to the respective risk in task 2.2, reflecting the sustainability dimension to what they have the greatest impact. This stage involved an interactive process where the consortium researchers suggested and discussed the classification of actions until consensus was reached. Six researchers were responsible for conducting the actions classification process. Finally, the classification was validated by experts during the workshop. A circular representation of the three sustainability dimensions, using colours to differentiate them, was adopted to facilitate the visualization of the actions, as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 9: Representation of the sustainability dimensions

As a second step, the actions were grouped into the resilience capabilities and represented in the circle as “slices”, as shown in Figure 13. The same content analysis approach used to classify the actions into the sustainability dimensions was applied here. As previously mentioned, as the focus was on the identification of proactive actions, the capabilities response and recovery were aggregate, as they represent the reactive actions.

Figure 13: Representation of the resilience capabilities

Finally, to present the sustainability dimensions and the resilience capabilities in a single model, the two circles were superimposed as presented in Figure 14. The model was named “Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar” as it aims to help supply chain actors to define the most appropriate strategy, as a set of actions to the context of the supply chain. Thus, each action is positioned in this radar according to its main contribution in terms of sustainability and resilience.

Figure 14 – Model developed to represent the action into the sustainability dimensions and resilience capabilities

VALIDATION WORKSHOP

As previously mentioned, the developed sustainability and resilience model was validated through an online workshop with experts from the EU (both from academia and industry) on topics related to SC management and performance. The workshop took place on September 12, 2023, and had 41 participants.

After initial presentations of the project and the task, the experts were randomly engaged in small groups of similar size in order to avoid bias and possible variations of interpretations, and each group worked on one slice of the radar (i.e., group 1 worked on readiness along sustainability dimensions). The experts were asked to review the actions, discuss their position within the sustainability dimensions and resilience capabilities – the strategies – and, if necessary, provide inputs on possible synergies and trade-offs with other sustainability dimensions and resilience capabilities. A collaborative platform was used to allow all participants to interact and make suggestions. Following the project partners instructions, they could move the actions to other parts of the radar and include new actions, as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15 – Example of collaborative board used during the workshop

The following instructions were provided:

1. Identify actions that have impact on other resilience capability and/or sustainability dimension (move the related “post it” from one radar slice to another);
2. Are there actions that can cause trade-offs between resilience and sustainability? How to avoid or smooth the negative impact? (use pink post its, write the ID of the related action and place it in the radar slice with trade-off);
3. Is there any other action that you think should be included? (use yellow post its to include new actions).

Experts agreed with the content of the identified actions presented, despite having some differences regarding their positioning. Moreover, experts had fruitful discussions on the multiple effects of some actions. For example, S_3 – “Provide training programs to low-skilled workers and involve them in order to increase their participation to training activities” – was originally categorized within the economic sustainability pillar related to the resilience capability of market strength. Yet, after a lengthy discussion, experts agreed to switch this action to the social sustainability pillar given that it is the more prevalent dimension of the action, despite maintaining that it had a secondary effect on the economic pillar. Overall, 23 actions were either moved or had a secondary effect identified during the workshop.

Apart from the positioning discussions, experts also evaluated if certain actions required a trade-off between strategies, particularly between sustainability and resilience or between two different resilience capabilities. This was the case, for instance, with L_11 – “Increased mandatory post-market surveillance to ensure better product safety, minimize risks and fines, and also protect image.” – originally placed under the economic sustainability pillar of the market strength resilience capability. After some exchange of arguments, experts agreed that this action could increase costs related to Product Lifecycle Management, especially on the post-market stage, which could hinder their capacity for economic sustainability under the readiness resilience capability. Another interesting example is EN_15 – “Creating an extensive supplier network with alternative options/routes and following the principle of local rather than global to be more responsive and sustainable in the short term.” – an economically sustainable action with flexible resilient capability, which could represent an issue especially in the case of local suppliers having increased costs to

access particular resources and raw materials, i.e., a negative trade-off for the economic sustainability of financial strength resilience capability. Altogether, 8 actions had trade-offs with other strategies.

The result was the final list of more than 100 validated actions located in the Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar according to their main contribution in terms of sustainability and resilience.

4. RESULTS

The results of the work carried out in T2.3 help the identification of actions, and formulation of strategies thanks to a comprehensive and integrative model. This section presents the results divided into three parts:

- Clustering of actions for supply chain sustainability and resilience;
- Model “Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar”;
- Principles and guidelines on how to use the model.

ACTIONS FOR SUPPLY CHAIN SUSTAINABILITY AND RESILIENCE

The Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar encompasses more that 100 actions grouped according to their contribution to the sustainability dimensions and the resilience capabilities. The strategies represent the combination of the sustainability dimensions and the resilience capabilities, with the intent to combine actions that have effects on both aspects following the understanding that current and future supply chains require more modular and interconnected approaches in detriment of the traditional stand-alone strategies.

Since the actions derived from diverse and heterogenous risks, the choice for the actions to be implemented must consider the context of each supply chain and the priorities of its actors. Thus, supply chain actors can adopt only part of the actions within a strategy and/or can combine actions from different strategies according to their specific needs. The following tables (2 to 21) present the actions grouped by strategies.

Table 2 – Actions for economic sustainability and flexibility

Economic/Flexibility: This strategy intends to support the development of the capacity of supply chains to adapt its business processes and models to face disruptions related to (or with consequence to) economic aspects. Actions linked to flexible infrastructure, flexible and alternative suppliers' base, work force flexibility, production scheduling and logistics are examples of aspects to be explored in this strategy in order to increase responsiveness.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_15	Adopt technology-driven solutions for production scheduling (such as, Adaptive and self-organised scheduling, Big-data driven scheduling, collaborative scheduling)	
EN_15	Creating an extensive supplier network with alternative options/routes and following the principle of local rather than global to be more responsive and sustainable in the short term.	
EN_17	Improve storage infrastructure and adapt to changing conditions to maintain the quality of products, especially for fragile products such as food.	
S_8	Provide new metrics and models for SC reconfigurability (modularity, integrability, convertibility, ...)	

S_29	Consolidate consignment and introduce flexible delivery time windows to improve the distribution process.	
S_31	Update the conventional supply chain curriculum with the technology-oriented supply chain management content.	
EN_23	Participate in sharing economies; diversify supplier structure to assure availability of resources.	
S_12	Adopt flexible job rotation	
EN_3	Promote the independence of the units, organizational adaptation, network reconfiguration and diversification of the supplier structure to reduce dependence on third-party suppliers (maintaining when necessary or advantageous for all involved).	

Table 3 – Actions for environmental sustainability and flexibility

Environmental/Flexibility: This strategy aims to promote a greater ability to adapt to changes in light of unforeseen circumstances that could have an influence on environmental challenges. The strategy increases the adaptability of manufacturing, materials, and work to solve environmental problems. Implementing technologies like augmented reality and 3D printing is crucial to provide firms with new options for changing their business practices.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_28	Make use of augmented and virtual reality and 3D printing to offer try-before-you-buy solutions, and to produce innovative and environment friendly packages.	
S_38	Revamp career programming and job definitions to be as climate and sustainability -related as possible and within multidisciplinary teams.	
EN_8	Research and develop sustainable materials and resources in collaboration with supply chain partners to reduce vulnerability to shortages.	

Table 4 – Actions for social sustainability and flexibility

Social/Flexibility: This strategy focuses on flexibility regarding workforce and social aspects through actions that stimulate diversity, allow adaptive organizational structures and promoting free labour movements. It is also important to implement job rotation and fit-for-purpose learning system.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_37	Implement job-rotation assignments and a fit-for-purpose all-age learning system with mentor support.	
P_20	Cultivate adaptive – rather than hierarchical – organizational and supply chain structures that support rapid change, refocusing, and reallocation of resources.	
S_30	Diversify the workforce and consider the importance of advertising a challenging job with work-life balance to attract and retain talent.	
S_35	Take advantage of free labour movements as a supply of foreign workers to fill the unattained jobs	
L_18	Target training programs for disadvantaged groups in the workforce to increase inclusion. This creates a broader, more resilient labor base and mitigates the risk of skills shortages.	

Table 5 – Actions for economic sustainability and integration/visibility

Economic/Integration Visibility - This strategy strengthens the visibility and integration of economic sustainability by promoting the quality and quantity of internal and external information exchange and establishing and reinforcing transparent business relationships. Investment in research and development, introduction of new technologies, and a redefinition of the used resources are examples of important types of actions for this strategy. The introduction of digital roadmaps and the definition of data requirements are essential.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_2	Ensure security in communication (e.g., through encryption), monitor system-threatening actions, implement regular system updates, ensure data privacy, access control and authentication protocol, ensure wireless systems encrypted (for instance, use blockchain to ensure anonymity and confidentiality)	
T_17	Establish data structure agreements between SC partners	
T_19	Define data requirements aligned with the companies' business model and develop a data management model needed for the supply chain's operations and business processes	
EN_4	Establish and reinforce transparent business relationships also enabled through blockchain-based traceability	
EN_9	Invest in research and development, collaboration and networking with other companies, small-scale pilots, flexible technology strategies with open systems to seamlessly integrate other technologies, use of open source.	
EN_20	Improve transparency over capacity through technology implementation (artificial intelligence, DLT, ...) to share and sell surplus capacity of their assets along the supply chain.	
L_5	Use an automated, secure platform to monitor supply chain processes. For example, an open blockchain where employees hold digital certificates can lead to cost-effective monitoring instead of costly random monitoring.	
P_25	Use new technologies to improve the transparency of the supply chain, connecting all of its information and components. Develop pre-contracts and map possible partners, or use digital technologies to establish intelligent contracts, once opportunism is detected.	
S_4	Use off chain data storing systems (cloud and fog computing for data storage and processing) for integrating with smart city environment	
S_10	Increase SC visibility and transparency through the use of track and trace technologies (i.e., product unique identifiers like RFID, QR code); follow events across the supply chain (e.g., GPS); and reporting and analysing information (e.g., blockchain, big data, and analytics).	
S_19	Implement an omnichannel strategy that provides visibility of a variety of elements (e.g., product, demand, shipment, returns) in an integrated manner.	
S_32	Encourage the collaboration between departments and HR in preparing the HR infrastructure (e.g., defining future roles, reviewing organisational learning).	
T_3	Create environments that allow the integration of systems, forming a System-of-Systems (SoS), based on aspects such as: self-adaptation, self-organisation, self-maintenance, self-awareness, self-prediction and self-reconfiguration. The use of digital twins can help to make smart decisions through real-time communication and cooperation between humans, machines, smart equipment, sensors, etc	
T_7	Promote collaborative (rather than competitive) strategies concerning infrastructure developments required for the adoption of digital technologies (especially between large and small companies)	
T_18	Define technology adoption roadmap in accordance with the company's business model in order to optimize the quantity, quality and timeliness of the information shared between SC partners	

Table 6 – Actions for environmental sustainability and integration/visibility

Environmental/ Integration/visibility: The aim of this strategy is to achieve higher levels of visibility regarding environmental issues through actions where collaboration is encouraged, and track and trace technologies are applied to boost transparency on environmental practices.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_11	Formalise information in Digital product passport (mandatory by 2024 in textile, construction, batteries). Managers should proactively reconfigure data flows to account for decision-making in a reverse supply chain.	High
S_18	Collaborate with logistic service providers for the implementation of environmental sustainability practices, implement coordinated logistics and transportation programs, certification and green goals; develop environmental auditing and management systems; cooperate with customer and suppliers	Medium
EN_21	Tracking of energy sources and consumptions along the supply chain via Distributed Ledger Technology/blockchain.	Medium
S_6	Use unmanned aerial vehicles applications to monitor and measure air pollution levels	Medium

Table 7 – Actions for social sustainability and integration/visibility

Social/Integration/visibility: Collaboration, information sharing, and integration are essential characteristics of current supply chains. This strategy creates value for stakeholders by a combination of actions related to information sharing with all supply chain partners. Cybersecurity measures are required to protect all parts involved. Big data analytics and blockchain are also important technologies for this strategy.		
ID	Action	Priority
E_12	Increase Ethical and CSR strategy and practices to gain customers' trust and improve satisfaction	High
T_1	Establish confidentiality agreements between SC partners that focus on privacy of data exchange; and define cyber-security measures supported by decentralized technologies. Requires suitable regulatory frameworks.	High
EN_1	Create a clear data basis for analysing working conditions, including the effects of climate change. Improve transparency along supply chains using technologies such as sensors, DLT, blockchain, etc.	Medium
L_15	Increase vigilance and pressure on suppliers, forcing an end to child labour through wholesale pricing. Engage SC actors in activities related to visibility and social sustainability in order to ensure good practices from end to end of the SCs.	Medium
P_13	Develop cybersecurity measures supported by decentralised technologies. Establish confidentiality agreements between SC partners and/or adopt zero trust supply chains based on the zero-trust philosophy in cyber and information technology security.	Medium
P_15	Establish a clear communication agenda between managers and workers to de-escalate workers anxiety.	Medium
S_16	Encourage involvement for promoting appropriate legislation about social sustainability, educate external actors about social concerns; Provide transparency about social sustainability; Establish feedback gathering systems to involve stakeholders	Medium
S_17	Share regular updates with consumers about breakthroughs in procurement that favors ethical sourcing and responsible manufacturing; Enhance preparedness for new regulation (EPR - Extended Producer Responsibility); educate workers about humanitarian and social supply chains (so they can contribute more effectively and efficiently to different social initiatives); implement technologies (BT, Social media, CPS, BDA) for enhancing transparency, trust in social practices and knowledge; Coordinate with multi-tier SC partners	Medium
L_13	Consider end-user concerns about data collection, educate customers about how their data will be handled to avoid misunderstandings and build trust.	Medium

L_19	Expand supplier evaluations to include gender equality criteria and introduce supplier guidelines regarding diversity management. This forces suppliers to actively work to reduce gender inequalities and reduces the risk of image damage due to unequal gender ratios in the supply chain.	
------	---	--

Table 8 – Actions for economic sustainability and market strength

Economic/Market Strength: This strategy intends to strengthen the aspects that affect the market position of the company with actions that aim to increase stakeholders' satisfaction and commitment to sustainability goals. There is a central concern for human-centred approaches to products design and internal developments.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_13	Educate consumer about product life extension; Create redistribution market to cater to the responsible consumers; Provide sustainability reporting, promote transparency through blockchain-based platforms; Build marketing campaign and improve communication; Use storytelling for communicating the sustainable value proposition	
L_11	Increased mandatory post-market surveillance to ensure better product safety, minimize risks and fines, and protect image.	
S_9	Use LARGS criteria (lean, agile, resilient, green and sustainable) for supplier selection	
S_34	Adopt knowledge transfer initiatives, such as: succession plans regularly monitored, mentoring programs and ad-hoc training, knowledge-based IT initiatives (e.g., open enterprise social networks)	

Table 9 – Actions for environmental sustainability and market strength

Environmental/ Market Strength: This strategy focuses on promoting market strength through actions that increase the environmental sustainability position of the company and the product. Waste management and the adoption of circular practices in the supply chain are considered essential aspects of this strategy, which recognizes that the market increasingly recognizes (and penalizes) companies according to their environmental practices.		
ID	Action	Priority
T_5	Increase the use of circular supply chain models such as refuse, rethink, reduce, reuse, remanufacture and repair. Ensure that products in the end-of-life (that cannot be part of the previous strategies) are recycled.	
EN_6	Increase use of circular supply chain models, especially based on R strategies such as waste, rethink and reduce, recycle.	
L_16	Investment in new waste management infrastructure and associated maintenance activities for compliance through financial investment, stakeholder engagement and innovation.	
L_12	Marketing improvements to find other ways to engage consumers in the return process and reverse logistics to avoid emissions and still maintain customer loyalty.	
L_4	High investments in new technologies and improvement of processes to comply with new regulations and to avoid the reputation of greenwashing.	

Table 10 – Actions for social sustainability and market strength

Social/Market Strength: Social concerns are related to workers and customers satisfaction and the promotion of the relations between them and the other intervenients of supply chains. This strategy presupposes a human-centred perspective and intends to define communication options and develop initiatives, mechanisms, tools and methods that protect future workers.		
--	--	--

ID	Action	Priority
S_36	Change the dialogue surrounding supply chain and manufacturing since people perceive them as dirty, low-wage, and conventional industries.	
S_40	Design tools/methods for future workers through on-site access for applied learning of students, project works for high education institutions, and implementation of teaching Factory framework	
P_14	Develop welfare initiatives involving supply chain partners to avoid social anxiety due to labour market instability.	
P_21	Construct market-protected spaces via three forms of institutional work: retraining the jurisdiction of the market logic, infusing the responsible management logic with nonmarket elements, and maintaining market-protected spaces against resistance.	
E_8	Increase consumers' trust through appropriate structural assurance mechanisms, such as guarantees, quality disclosure	
P_22	Cultivate a cultural framework that fosters resilience, fairness, ethics, legality, and legitimacy within the labour market, thus preventing the growth of informal economies within the supply chain ecosystem.	
S_3	Provide training programs to low-skilled workers and motivate them to participate	
S_23	Adopt standards such as ISO 25550–2022 that provides requirements and guidelines to achieve age-inclusive workforce	

Table 11 – Actions for economic sustainability and efficiency

Economic/Efficiency: The strategy related to the development of efficient and economically sustainable supply chains involves increasing companies' productivity and optimization, with a clear focus on process innovation. The adoption of intelligent logistics solutions, by the implementation of technologies such as collaborative robots, sensors and blockchain is an example of a fundamental aspect.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_43	Adopt technologies that contributes to enhance last-mile delivery practices in urban settings, such as delivery robots and unmanned aerial vehicles applications for real time information, monitoring traffic. Integrate data from different sources through IoT to improve routing, optimise transportation, assure sustainable urban freight logistics	
EN_7	Increasing efficiency through more innovative production processes and the use of technologies to reduce costs.	
EN_16	Include the risks of environmental factors when designing supply chain structure	
L_1	Implementing services supported by digital technologies such as blockchain, DLT, digital currencies for contracting/payments (digital currencies on decentralized approaches)	
L_7	Move towards management-based regulation practices which rely on self-reporting, reducing bureaucratic burden. Also, tie regulation to technical standards by independent bodies.	
P_17	Strengthen short supply chains, local supplies, manufacturing and distribution innovations to face economic instability.	
P_18	Analyse production problems and management issues to find ways to make production better during political instability	
S_33	Set-up cross-functional teams to increase the collective understanding of the system, proactively solve problems, and minimize “data latency”.	
T_22	Adopt strategies that ensure that automation investments decisions are based on a balance between costs and benefits (including social and environmental gains), considering aspects	

	such as: optimization of workers time; acceleration of processes; increase quality of data, improve customer experience, environmental and social impact	
E_11	Promote quality and quantity of internal and external information exchange. Enable efficient and effective S&OP through advanced data analytics	
S_1	Increase investments in advanced technologies that contribute to increasing worker productivity (such as collaborative robots, wearables, skeletons, safety devices) using a socio-technical systems perspective that ensures the alignment between technical and social aspects, including a human-centred approach	

Table 12 – Actions for environmental sustainability and efficiency

Environmental/Efficiency: The strategy that promotes efficiency in environmental matters is related to waste reduction and a good use of resources, for instance, focusing on practices that address transportation (e.g., green logistics), storage and energy efficiency.		
ID	Action	Priority
T_20	Implement a data management model (including storage, sharing and security) that optimizes energy consumption	
EN_5	Implement green logistics practices (such as environmentally friendly packaging, transportation, and storage) to increase sustainability and efficiency.	
EN_11	Utilize alternative fuels and other renewable energy sources. Use green hydrogen as energy storage.	
EN_12	Creating a sustainable food supply chain by thinking regionally instead of globally, using renewable energy and new technologies to avoid emissions and losses.	
S_7	Provide proper routing schemes to establish energy efficiency and consistency in an IoT network	
P_23	Use Transport Management Systems to assist companies in the planning and optimization of the physical movement of goods.	

Table 13 – Actions for social sustainability and efficiency

Social/Efficiency: The goal of this strategy is the pursuit of effective ways to manage social aspects within and outside . Ensure focus on a human-centred approach is essential. The adoption and investment in new technologies like blockchain, robots, and digital devices are fundamental.		
ID	Action	Priority
S_4	Increase investments in advanced technologies, such as collaborative robots, wearables, skeletons, safety devices, using a socio-technical systems perspective that ensures the alignment between technical and social aspects, including a human-centred approach	
S_26	Give ownership of projects and let the new generations know their feedback is valued and acted upon	
S_27	Regulate and observe remote workers' workday to prevent them overlapping work and personal activities	
S_41	Use technologies (e.g., blockchain) in preventing deceptive recruitment, "providing transparency into working conditions and offering the ability to verify fair pay and working conditions"	
S_25	Develop training or mentor programs to combat with stress and lessen feelings of both role conflict and ambiguity.	

S_24	Create specific value for each employee based on what would be valuable to each different employee (e.g., inspiration, vigilance)	
------	---	--

Table 14 – Actions for economic sustainability and financial strength

Economic/Financial Strength: This strategy intends to strengthen the issues that affect the market position of companies by favouring better systems and tracking abilities. There is a central concern for developing skills on workers and consumers. Lastly, the adoption of new standards, collaboration will permit the fortification of the current market positioning and prepare it to be more resilient for future disruptions.		
ID	Action	Priority
EN_13	Create mechanisms to identify and manage the cost drivers in production, facilities and operations and improve visibility concerning suppliers (multi-tier) costs	
L_6	Reducing capital dependency through new payment methods with partner companies (Modern and faster payment systems, reduced barriers to entry for more competition)	
L_9	Investing in new technology to reduce the transaction chain. Possible solution approach: Implementing the blockchain-technology into the supply chain finance. It leads to full traceable transactions and reduces the amount of involved parties	
E_4	Exploit combinations of supply chain finance solutions such as: accounts receivable financing, inventory financing and accounts payable financing in combination with traditional financing instruments (guaranteed financing and credit financing).	
E_17	Exploit the information generated by operational activities to optimize financing activities (cross-border financial guarantee instruments).	
L_2	Coordinate funding schemes with regulatory changes to increase the chances of success of high-risk innovations	

Table 15 – Actions for environmental sustainability and financial strength

Environmental/Financial Strength: The strategy related to environmental concerns and financial strength is based on diversification, consistency, and availability. This strategy intends to increase the use of technology to analysis the financial performance of the new recycling measures.		
ID	Action	Priority
L_17	Technology scouting and analysis to determine financial performance of the new recycling technology	
P_24	Participate in green finance initiatives using green finance mechanisms and/or supporting credit for sustainable development	

Table 16 – Actions for economic sustainability and redundancy

Economic/Redundancy: This strategy aims to increase economic response by identifying and promoting adaptive changes to the supply chains and introducing actions that secure supply chain actors' revenue.		
ID	Action	Priority
E_1	Identify and promote adaptive changes to the supply chains (re-design, situational re-planning and dynamic re-scheduling, multi-region supplier, multi-sourcing, reserved inventory, and alternative shipment)	
P_26	Introduce insurance products for commodities to secure supply chain actors' revenues.	

S_20	Integrate the inventory with returns and sales channels, as well as suppliers, to oversee current stocks. Use AI and big data to foresee inventory requirements.	
------	--	--

Table 17 – Actions for environmental sustainability and redundancy

Environmental/Redundancy: This strategy intends to provide redundancy capacity in environmental matters by reducing dependencies and vulnerabilities of SC actors, for instance, through the adoption of diversity strategies in the energy portfolio based on renewable sources and investment in circular supply chain models and eco-design.		
ID	Action	Priority
T_4	Invest in circular supply chain models and eco-design in order to reduce dependencies on raw materials; ensure the collaboration between design teams and suppliers; develop alternative suppliers and alternative materials and components; reduce dependencies on geographically distant suppliers and on suppliers located in regions with major environmental and social risks; increase collaboration and visibility among product design, procurement and supply chain management	
T_11	Adopt diversity strategies in the energy portfolio based on renewable sources in order to reduce dependencies and vulnerabilities	

Table 18 – Actions for economic sustainability and readiness

Economic/Readiness - This strategy has an impact on economic sustainability and resilience readiness and is based on preventing and detecting problems in supply chains through defensive actions and collaboration. There is a special attention to increase security and risk detection. Readiness can be also assured by adopting solutions based on disruptive technologies, such as decentralized based systems, AI, machine learning and digital twins.		
ID	Action	Priority
E_14	Implement collaborative framework to facilitate co-production of cybersecurity guidance. Adopt a fully decentralized blockchain-based system that protects data security, privacy, and remove single point of failures of traditional SCs.	
EN_14	Develop effective risk management practices and early warning systems for extreme weather events to reroute supply chain routes early to reduce costs of downtime, delays and loss of goods.	
T_2	Develop skills and capacities to create the next generation operators (Operator4.0 and Operator5.0)	
T_9	Define cyber-security measures supported by decentralized technologies.	
T_16	Promote collaborative actions with the academy for training and specialization of personnel in data management and analysis	
EN_19	Increase research and development to find innovative solutions to address the impacts of climate change on storage conditions.	
L_3	Invest in cybersecurity to avoid loss of sensitive data, damage to the reputation of customers, high financial losses up to business interruptions and legal consequences.	
P_12	Deploy actions regarding the management dimension of the company: Maintain adequate buffer stock, employ multiple supplier sources, Construct risk emergency mechanism, Establishing a feasible incentive system. Diversify sourcing through expanded production and accessing known critical raw materials reserves	
L_14	Monitor risks derived from the adoption of obsolete business models	
T_12	Structure a strategy to ensure proactivity regarding regulatory frameworks	

E_3	Invest in digital transformation to increase the adaptability and capabilities to face fast market evolution.	
E_10	Usage of Partial Credit Guarantees (PCG) to solve cash flow interruptions.	
E_15	Concentrate defensive actions on supply chains end-to-end, reducing vulnerabilities in less-secure components of a system's supply chain. Balance technology adoption with management of SCRM process to avoid dependency from technology providers.	
E_16	Build IT infrastructures for full implementation of digital economy with capital investment and involvement of SC functions for cybersecurity.	

Table 19 – Actions for environmental sustainability and readiness

<p>Environmental/Readiness: For SC actors to be ready for environmental disruptions there is a need of a strategy that focuses on readiness and be concern with regulatory matters derived from current and future technological and societal characteristics. This strategy must insure the development of collaboration and stronger infrastructures. Technologies more associated with this strategy are AI, machine learning and digital twins.</p>		
ID	Action	Priority
T_13	Develop skills/training programs related to: the use of technologies related to technical features of alternative energy sources; and weather forecasting, namely innovation in very short-term forecasting and advances in uncertainty forecasting products	
EN_18	Create a robust monitoring system for storage facilities to detect potential problems early to prevent losses and quality degradation. (Regular inspections, monitoring temperature and humidity conditions, and use of sensor technologies for real-time monitoring).	
P_16	Design of incentive mechanisms and tokenization to promote consumer green behaviour.	
T_8	Using AI, machine learning and digital twins for predictive maintenance of the infrastructure	
T_10	Constantly develop and update regulatory frameworks aligned with current and future technological and societal characteristics, based on collaboration with affected stakeholders (policy makers). Structure a strategy to ensure proactivity regarding regulatory frameworks (SC actors).	

Table 20 – Actions for social sustainability and readiness

<p>Social/Readiness: This strategy aims to prevent and detect disruptions in supply chains by developing and promoting workers' and costumers' conditions and decrease security issues. The definition of a digital strategy that assures innovation through the use of digital technologies such as Distributed Ledger Technology and sensors, intends to promote the analysis of working conditions, predict different scenarios, and build a robust risk management process.</p>		
ID	Action	Priority
E_13	Develop a robust risk management process for demand variability and plan diversification strategies responsive to shifts in customer preferences and to better meet customers' expectations and enter new markets.	
S_39	Promote reskill and upskill of workers through: college education, lifelong learning and/or non-traditional options (employer sponsored on the job training, seminar, self-study open course programs, certification or re-certification), learning programmes with flexible working conditions	
T_21	Develop different and specialized skill sets that are not performed by "machines" (such as handling exceptional scenarios, creativity, and designing). Requires adequate instructors and training programs for which government, society and organizations may not yet be prepared	

E_7	Increase innovation-related training for technical staff for digital economy implementation by investing in HR, knowledge flows and R&D	
P_19	Build supply chain network models to provide insights on different scenarios in terms of dependencies on government support.	
S_5	Activate the moral self-awareness of the customers on working conditions	
S_21	Managers need to spend time with the business units of activities outsourced to understand potential security threats.	
S_22	Develop upskilling and training programs for newly-created technology and digitalisation - oriented skilled roles within the company	
P_27	Nurture the capabilities of employees and prepare them for the new challenges of cyber chains, risk awareness initiatives and training.	
E_5	Customer-based execution strategies (CBES) to create value for customers by enhancing customer engagement actions that lead to retrieving value from the customers directly.	
E_6	Design and implementation of a digital strategy considering both the operational strategy as well as the human resources strategy	

Table 21 – Actions for economic sustainability and response/recovery

Economic/Response and Recovery: The response in supply chains is addressed through this strategy by investing in develop tools to increase the response and recovery. Implementation of key industry 4.0 technologies such as Blockchain and Artificial Intelligence are essential to provoke decreases in economic losses resulting from disruptive events.		
ID	Action	Priority
E_2	Digitalize the SC (Blockchain, Big Data analysis – Power BI, smart contracts, NFTs, etc.) to enable collaboration and reduce the barriers to deploy a business intelligence environment for sharing and accessing information to corporate decision makers as well as operational team.	
E_9	Integrate SC processes with key industry 4.0 technologies to enable visibility and adaptability, such as Artificial Intelligence, Big Data Analytics and blockchain for real-time operations monitoring, production control and advanced planning & scheduling capabilities.	
L_8	Usage of early warning systems. Indicators should have accurate values, be highly generalized and comprehensive so that they can reflect the risks of cross-border payments	
S_14	Invest in demand forecasting to combat demand variability - use AI-enabled demand forecasting and analyse social media data for demand forecasting	

MODEL: SUPPLY CHAIN SUSTAINABILITY AND RESILIENCE RADAR

Finally, the model called “Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar”, presented in Figure 16, reflects the positioning of the actions according to their classification into the sustainability dimensions and the resilience capabilities.

Figure 16– Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar

USING THE MODEL

The Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar is a model that allows the exploration of actions in different ways. The aim is to make it easier for the “user” to find the actions, that can be consulted in Table 2. It is important to mention that the model was designed to be dynamic, meaning that new actions will be incorporated when appropriate, and current actions can be excluded if the probability and impact of the related risk are considered to decrease substantially.

Figure 17 presents the view of one specific strategy in the model (Economic and Integration/Visibility). This is considered the main view of the model as it allows the identification of the actions that contribute to a specific combination of sustainability dimension and resilience capability.

Figure 17 – View of a strategy

The actions can also be explored in terms of each single sustainability dimension. In this case, the user can identify the actions that are part of the economic, environmental and social dimensions, as shown in Figure 18 and define a plan to tackle issues from a critical dimension in the context of their specific supply chain. in a given period of time.

Figure 18 – View of the actions by sustainability dimension

Similarly, the actions can be explored in terms of resilience capabilities, as shown in Figure 19. In this case, a company can decide to tackle a specific resilience capability and explore the suggested actions.

Figure 19: View of the actions by resilience capability

Another possible way to navigate the radar is to start from risks related to a specific issue for the supply chain. In this case, the user can choose all the actions specifically for this issue and identify a path along the resilience capabilities and sustainability dimensions across the radar. As an example, in the following chart (Fig. 20), the user has selected all the actions related to training to cope with the issue of knowledge loss and missing skills, derived from different megatrends and trends, such as the ageing and young population boom or the advent of a new digital and knowledge-based society.

Figure 20: View of the actions to face a specific issue.

The set of actions selected increase mainly the readiness capability but also efficiency and flexibility of the supply chains (see for example S_25, i.e., “Develop training or mentor programs to combat with stress and lessen feelings of both role conflict and ambiguity” which improves workers’ skills as well as workers efficiency).

In addition to increase the resilience of the SC, these actions have a predominant impact on the social sustainability of the SC, as they push “organisations to provide equitable opportunities, encourage diversity, promote connectedness within and outside the community, ensure the quality of life and provide democratic processes and accountable governance structures” (Gimenez et al., 2012).

As an example, the action S_39, i.e., “Promote reskill and upskill of workers through college education, lifelong learning and/or non-traditional options (employer sponsored on the job training, seminar, self-study open course programs, certification or re-certification), learning programs with flexible working conditions” increases the readiness of the SC by promoting training programs which favour knowledge transfer within the SC and the community, and it also increases the social sustainability of the SC by developing the human resources and by giving them the opportunities to receive training through flexible working conditions.

Finally, to provide a guideline to navigate this way to use the radar, the full list of actions related to training has been provided in Table 22 below.

Table 22– Actions related to training activities/programs.

ID	Training related actions	Action related strategy
----	--------------------------	-------------------------

T_21	Develop different and specialized skill sets that are not performed by "machines" (such as handling exceptional scenarios, creativity, and designing). Requires adequate instructors and training programs for which government, society and organizations may not yet be prepared	Social/Readiness
S_22	Develop upskilling and training programs for newly created technology and digitalization -oriented skilled roles within the company	Social/Readiness
S_39	Promote reskill and upskill of workers through college education, lifelong learning and/or non-traditional options (employer sponsored on the job training, seminar, self-study open course programs, certification or re-certification), learning programs with flexible working conditions	Social/Readiness
L_18	Target training programs for disadvantaged groups in the workforce to increase inclusion. This creates a broader, more resilient labor base and mitigates the risk of skills shortages.	Social/Readiness
E_7	Increase innovation-related training for technical staff for digital economy implementation by investments in HR, knowledge flows and R&D	Social/Readiness
P_27	Nurture the capabilities of employees and prepare them for the new challenges cyber chains, risk awareness initiatives and training.	Social/Readiness
S_25	Develop training or mentor programs to combat with stress and lessen feelings of both role conflict and ambiguity.	Social/Efficiency
T_2	Develop skills and capacities to create the next generation operators (Operator4.0 and Operator5.0)	Economic/Readiness
T_16	Promote collaborative actions with the academy for training and specialization of personnel in data management and analysis	Economic/ Readiness
T_13	Develop skills/training programs related to the use of technologies related to technical features of alternative energy sources; and weather forecasting, namely innovation in very short-term forecasting and advances in uncertainty forecasting products	Environmental/Readiness

1. CONCLUSIONS

Task 2.3 "Definition of SC strategies for resilience and sustainability" results are presented in this report. The objective of this comprehensive work was to propose strategies that businesses and supply chains may use to improve their social, environmental, and economic sustainability as well as their resilience to unforeseen events. One of the fundamental issues in supply chain management is the dynamic nature of its structures and processes. In the complex context of relationships between partners and the long and dispersed supply chains that characterize today's business environments, a diversity of aspects is interconnected, including sustainability and resilience.

In the past years, the focus of supply chain sustainability research has been mainly devoted to reducing environmental implications of supply chains, often quantified in terms of greenhouse gas emissions and resource consumptions. Parallely, literature on supply chain resilience has mainly addressed how to return to the initial stage after the occurrence of a crisis. This study aims to go beyond this partial approach with a more comprehensive and balanced perspective that acknowledges that maintaining business continuity (through persisting, adapting or transforming), to reduce long-term risks is a common aspect of sustainability and resilience.

Considering that the risks identified in Task 2.2 reflect the most important issues in the existing and future supply chain environments, the analysis of potential responses to these risks served as the

starting point for the development of actions. A systematic search for prior publications was used to find strategies to address those risks. As a result of this extensive research, more than 100 actions were identified covering a wide range of themes that are pertinent to contemporary environments.

After that, the actions were grouped according to their contribution to the three sustainability dimensions and the resilience capabilities. Thus, the research provides a novel concept, named the "Supply Chain Sustainability and Resilience Radar," which enables supply chain actors to explore the actions from different perspectives to choose the most effective strategy for their situation.

The model is intended to be flexible and dynamic, so new actions can be included when appropriate and current actions may be deleted if it is thought that the probability and impact of the associated risk have significantly decreased. Moreover, the study contributes to literature by shedding light on the resilience capabilities and sustainability dimensions which need to be further investigated in order to understand which actions could be adopted to increase them. Finally, the task contributes to practice by providing a guidance through the research findings to managers in the European setting to deal with the complexity and uncertainty of supply chains.

REFERENCES

- Chowdhury, M.M.H. & Quaddus, M. (2016), Supply chain readiness, response and recovery for resilience. *Supply Chain Management*, 21(6), 709-731. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/SCM-12-2015-0463>.
- Chowdhury, M.M.H. & Quaddus, M. (2017), Supply chain resilience: Conceptualization and scale development using dynamic capability theory. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 188, 185-204. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2017.03.020>.
- Costa F.H.O., Moraes, C.C., Silva, A.L., Delai, I., Chaudhuri, A., & Preira, C.R (2022). Does resilience reduce food waste? Analysis of Brazilian supplier-retailer dyad. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 338, 130488. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130488>.
- Denyer, D., & Tranfield, T. (2009). Producing a systematic review. In D. A. Buchanan & A. Bryman (Eds.), *The Sage Handbook of Organizational Research Methods*. London: Sage.
- Elkington, J. (1994). Towards the sustainable corporation: win-win-win business strategies for sustainable development. *California Management Review*, 36(2), 90-100. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/41165746>.
- European Commission (2022). Sustainable Development. Available at: https://policy.trade.ec.europa.eu/development-and-sustainability/sustainable-development_en. Accessed in May 2023.
- Gibson, C. B., & Birkinshaw, J. (2004). The antecedents, consequences, and mediating role of organizational ambidexterity. *Academy of Management Journal*, 47(2), 209-226. DOI: 10.2307/20159573.
- He, Z. L., & Wong, P. K. (2004). Exploration vs. exploitation: An empirical test of the ambidexterity hypothesis. *Organization Science*, 15(4), 481-494. DOI: 10.1287/orsc.1040.0078.
- Holling, C.S. (1973) Resilience and Stability in Ecological Systems. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 4, 1-23. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1146/annurev.es.04.110173.000245>.
- Ivanov, D. (2018). Revealing interfaces of supply chain resilience and sustainability: a simulation study. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(10), 3507-3523, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2017.1343507>.
- Ji, L., Chunlin, Y., Taiwen, F. & Wang, C. (2020). Achieving the environmental profits of green supplier integration: The roles of supply chain resilience and knowledge combination. *Sustainable Development*, 28(4), 978-989. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2050>.
- Lee, S. M., & Rha, J. S. (2016). Ambidextrous supply chain as a dynamic capability: building a resilient supply chain. *Management Decision*, 54(1), 2-23. DOI: 10.1108/md-12-2014-0674.
- March, J. G. (1991). Exploration and exploitation in organizational learning. *Organization Science*, 2(1), 71-87. DOI: 10.1287/orsc.2.1.71.
- Mahrjerdi, Y.Z., & Shafiee, M. (2021). A resilient and sustainable closed-loop supply chain using multiple sourcing and information sharing strategies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 289, 125141. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125141>.

Messina, D., Soares, A.L., Barros, A.C., & Zimmermann, R. How visible is your supply chain? A model for supply chain visibility assessment. *Supply Chain Forum: An International Journal*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/16258312.2022.2079955>.

Negri, M., Cagno, E. & Colicchia, C. (2022). Building sustainable and resilient supply chains: a framework and empirical evidence on trade-offs and synergies in implementation of practices. *Production Planning & Control*. DOI: [10.1080/09537287.2022.2053758](https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2022.2053758).

O'Reilly, C. A., & Tushman, M. L. (2008). Ambidexterity as a dynamic capability: Resolving the innovators dilemma. In A. P. Brief & B. M. Staw (Eds.), *Research in Organizational Behavior*, Vol 28: an Annual Series of Analytical Essays and Critical Reviews (Vol. 28, pp. 185-206). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riob.2008.06.002>.

Pu, G., Li, S. & Bai, J. (2023). Effect of supply chain resilience on firm's sustainable competitive advantage: a dynamic capability perspective. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(2), 4881-4898. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-22483-1>.

Rahman, T., Paul, S.K., Shukla, N., Agarwal, R., & Taghikhah, F. (2022). Supply chain resilience initiatives and strategies: A systematic review. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 170, 108317. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2022.108317>.

Sazvar, Z., Tafakkori, K., Oladzad, N., & Nayeri, S. (2021). A capacity planning approach for sustainable-resilient supply chain network design under uncertainty: A case study of vaccine supply chain. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 159, 107406. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2021.107406>.

Sheffi, Y. & Rice, J. (2005). A Supply Chain View of the Resilient Enterprise. *MIT Sloan Management Review* 47 (1): 41–48.

Silva, M., Pereira, M.M.O., & Hendry, L.C. (2023). Embracing change in tandem: resilience and sustainability together transforming supply chains. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 43(1), 166-196. DOI [10.1108/IJOPM-09-2022-0625](https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOPM-09-2022-0625).

Singh, R.J., Gupta, A., & Gunasekaran, A. (2018). Analysing the interaction of factors for resilient humanitarian supply chain. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(21), 6809-6827. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2018.1424373>.

Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18(7), 509-533. DOI: [10.1002/\(sici\)1097-0266\(199708\)18:7<509::aid-smj882>3.0.co;2-z](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1097-0266(199708)18:7<509::aid-smj882>3.0.co;2-z).

Uotila, J. (2017). Exploration, exploitation, and variability: Competition for primacy revisited. *Strategic Organization*, 15(4), 461-480. DOI: [10.1177/1476127017705103](https://doi.org/10.1177/1476127017705103).

Wieland, A., & Durach, C.F (2021). Two perspectives on supply chain resilience. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 42(3), 315-322. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbl.12271>.

Reference used for the identification of actions

- Assa, H., Sharifi, H., & Lyons, A. (2021). An examination of the role of price insurance products in stimulating investment in agriculture supply chains for sustained productivity. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 288(3), 918-934. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2020.06.030>
- Blühdorn, I., & Butzlaff, F. (2020). Democratization beyond the post-democratic turn: towards a research agenda on new conceptions of citizen participation. *Democratization*, 27(3), 369-388. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13510347.2019.1707808>
- Feng, X. P, Zhou, D. Zhang, Z. Chen, and S. Wang. (2022). The impact of trade policy on global supply chain network equilibrium: A new perspective of product-market chain competition," *Omega* (Westport), vol. 109, p. 102612, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.omega.2022.102612.
- Kellerhals, A., & Baumgartner, T. (Eds.). (2021). *Current Challenges of European Integration: 12th Network Europe Conference, 9–10 November 2020* (Vol. 211). buch & netz.
- Kumar, L.; Nadeem, F.; Sloan, M.; Restle-Steinert, J.; Deitch, M.J.; Ali Naqvi, S.; Kumar, A.; Sassanelli, C. (2022). Fostering Green Finance for Sustainable Development: A Focus on Textile and Leather Small Medium Enterprises in Pakistan. *Sustainability* 2022, 14, 11908. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141911908>
- Laker, B. (2020). *Why Collaboration Needs to Win Over Protectionism in A New World Post COVID-19*, Venice: Fondazione Università Ca' Foscari, 2020. doi: 10.30687/978-88-6969-442-4/029.
- Lee, S. S. Y., Lee, J. E., & Kim, K. S. (2020). Evaluating basic income, basic service, and basic voucher for social and ecological sustainability. *Sustainability*, 12(20), 8348."
- Li, X., Zhang, G., & Qi, Y. (2023). Differentiated environmental regulations and enterprise innovation: The moderating role of government subsidies and executive political experience. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02851-0>
- Nagurney, A., D. Besik, and D. Li, (2019). "Strict quotas or tariffs? Implications for product quality and consumer welfare in differentiated product supply chains," *Transp Res E Logist Transp Rev*, vol. 129, pp. 136–161, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tre.2019.07.008.
- Nagurney, A., D. Besik, and D. Li (2029). Strict quotas or tariffs? Implications for product quality and consumer welfare in differentiated product supply chains, *Transp Res E Logist Transp Rev*, vol. 129, pp. 136–161, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.tre.2019.07.008."
- Mishra, A.S., Prajapati, S.G. (2023). Adaptability of Management in Transportation Systems. In: Upadhyay, R.K., Sharma, S.K., Kumar, V., Valera, H. (eds) *Transportation Systems Technology and Integrated Management. Energy, Environment, and Sustainability*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-1517-0_19
- Schüßler, E. S., Lohmeyer, N., & Ashwin, S. (2022). "We can't compete on human rights": Creating market-protected spaces to institutionalize the emerging logic of responsible management. *Academy of Management Journal*, (ja). <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2020.1614>
- Webb, A., McQuaid, R., & Rand, S. (2020). Employment in the informal economy: Implications of the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 40(9/10), 1005-1019. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-08-2020-0371>
- Webb, A., McQuaid, R., & Rand, S. (2020). Employment in the informal economy: Implications of the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 40(9/10), 1005-1019. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSSP-08-2020-0371>

- Yosef, F. A., Jum'a, L., & Alatoon, M. (2023). Identifying and Categorizing Sustainable Supply Chain Practices Based on Triple Bottom Line Dimensions: Evaluation of Practice Implementation in the Cement Industry. *Sustainability*, 15(9), 7323. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097323>
- Hsu, C-H., A.-Y. Chang, T.-Y. Zhang, W.-D. Lin, and W.-L. Liu, (2021). Deploying Resilience Enablers to Mitigate Risks in Sustainable Fashion Supply Chains," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 5, p. 2943, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.3390/su13052943.
- Manikas, I., B. Sundarakani, F. Anastasiadis, and B. Ali (2022). A Framework for Food Security via Resilient Agri-Food Supply Chains: The Case of UAE," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 10, p. 6375, May 2022, doi: 10.3390/su14106375.
- OECD (2023). <https://www.oecd.org/ukraine-hub/policy-responses/the-supply-of-critical-raw-materials-endangered-by-russia-s-war-on-ukraine-e01ac7be/>
- Kosasih, E.E., Margaroli, F., Simone Gelli, Ajmal Aziz, Nick Wildgoose, Alexandra Brintrup. (2022) Towards knowledge graph reasoning for supply chain risk management using graph neural networks. *International Journal of Production Research*, pages 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2021.1884311>
- Ghadge, A., M. Weiß, N. D. Caldwell, and R. Wilding (2019). Managing cyber risk in supply chains: a review and research agenda," *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 223–240, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1108/SCM-10-2018-0357"
- Weber, T. J., Hydock, C., Ding, W., Gardner, M., Jacob, P., Mandel, N., ... & Van Steenburg, E. (2021). Political polarization: challenges, opportunities, and hope for consumer welfare, marketers, and public policy. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 40(2), 184-205. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0743915621991103>
- Esmailian, B., Sarkis, J., Lewis, K., & Behdad, S. (2020). Blockchain for the future of sustainable supply chain management in Industry 4.0. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 163, 105064. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105064>
- Zeng, K., Lu, Y., & Li, Y. W. (2021). Trade agreements and global value chain (GVC) participation: Evidence from Chinese industries. *Economics & Politics*, 33(3), 533-582. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecpo.12185>
- Sheu, J. B., Kundu, T., & Choi, T. M. (2021). International sustainable supply chain management under bilateral governments' policy intervention and power asymmetry. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2021.3108975>
- Paudel, D., Neupane, R. C., Sigdel, S., Poudel, P., & Khanal, A. R. (2023). COVID-19 Pandemic, Climate Change, and Conflicts on Agriculture: A Trio of Challenges to Global Food Security. *Sustainability*, 15(10), 8280. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15108280>
- Vanthourhout, H. (2019). The rise of outward direct investments by Chinese multinationals in the German automotive sector, a Global Production Network analysis, Université catholique de Louvain, Louvain, 2019.
- Božić, F.; Karasalihović Sedlar, D.; Smajla, I.; Ivančić, I. (2021). Analysis of Changes in Natural Gas Physical Flows for Europe via Ukraine in 2020. *Energies* 2021, 14, 5175. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14165175>
- Dadush, U. (2023). The policy response to global value chain disruption. *Global Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-5899.13220>

- Anne Posthuma & Arianna Rossi (2017) Coordinated governance in global value chains: supranational dynamics and the role of the International Labour Organization, *New Political Economy*, 22:2, 186-202. Doi: 10.1080/13563467.2016.1273342
- Sommerer, T., Agné, H., Zelli, F., & Bes, B. (2022). *Global legitimacy crises: decline and revival in multilateral governance*. Oxford University Press.
- Browne, K. E. (2022). Rethinking governance in international climate finance: Structural change and alternative approaches. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 13(5), e795. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.795>
- Ivanov, Dmitry & Dolgui, Alexandre. (2022). The shortage economy and its implications for supply chain and operations management. *International Journal of Production Research*. 60. 1-14. 10.1080/00207543.2022.2118889.
- Suryadi, A., & Rau, H. (2023). Considering region risks and mitigation strategies in the supplier selection process for improving supply chain resilience. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 181, 109288."
- OECD (2021). *Fostering economic resilience in a world of open and integrated markets - Risks, vulnerabilities and areas for policy actions*.
- Sodhi, M. S., Tang, C. S., & Willenson, E. T. (2021). Research opportunities in preparing supply chains of essential goods for future pandemics. *International Journal of Production Research*, 1-16."
- World Bank (2023). *Global Economic Prospects, January 2023*. Washington, DC: World Bank. doi:10.1586/978-1-4648-1906-3. License: Creative Commons Attribution CC BY 3.0 IGO
- OECD (2023). *Resilient supply chains*. <https://www.oecd.org/trade/resilient-supply-chains/>
- Patidar, A., Sharma, M., Agrawal, R., & Sangwan, K. S. (2023). Supply chain resilience and its key performance indicators: an evaluation under Industry 4.0 and sustainability perspective. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 34(4), 962-980.
- Shah, H. M., Gardas, B. B., Narwane, V. S., & Mehta, H. S. (2023). The contemporary state of big data analytics and artificial intelligence towards intelligent supply chain risk management: A comprehensive review. *Kybernetes*, 52(5), 1643-1697.
- Senna, P. P., Ferreira, L. M. D., Barros, A. C., Roca, J. B., & Magalhães, V. (2022). Prioritizing barriers for the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 171, 108428."
- Zhang, X., Shi, Y., Zhang, P., Xu, F., & Jiang, C. (2023). System dynamics modelling and robustness analysis for capital-constrained supply chain under disruption. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 123(2), 492-514.
- Sohag, K., Islam, M. M., Tomas Žiković, I., & Mansour, H. (2022). Food inflation and geopolitical risks: analyzing European regions amid the Russia-Ukraine war. *British Food Journal*."
- World Bank (2023). *Global Economic Prospects, January 2023*. Washington, DC: World Bank. doi:10.1586/978-1-4648-1906-3. License: Creative Commons Attribution CC BY 3.0 IGO.
- Urciuoli, L., Phan TTH, and Hints, J. (2024). Managing supply chain risks in emerging economies - the case of timber supply chains in Vietnam. *International Journal of Logistics Systems and Management* 1(1):1 DOI: 10.1504/IJLSM.2021.10044572 (accepted in 2022)"

- Yang, L., Huo, B., & Gu, M. (2022). The impact of information sharing on supply chain adaptability and operational performance. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 33(2), 590-619.
- Schlegel, A., Birkel, H. S., & Hartmann, E. (2021). Enabling integrated business planning through big data analytics: a case study on sales and operations planning. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 51(6), 607-633."
- Oner, C. (2023). Inflation prices on the rise, International Monetary Fund, <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/fandd/issues/Series/Back-to-Basics/Inflation>
- Guenette, Justin-Damien. (2020). Price Controls: Good Intentions, Bad Outcomes. Policy Research Working Paper;No. 9212. © World Bank, Washington, DC. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/33606> License: CC BY 3.0 IGO." "
- Chen, Li & Lee, Hau & Tang, Christopher. (2022). Supply chain fairness. *Production and Operations Management*. 31. 10.1111/poms.13849.
- Zighan, Saad & Alkalha, Ziad & Abualqumboz, Moheeb & Dwaikat, Nidal. (2021). The role of entrepreneurial orientation in developing SMEs resilience capabilities throughout COVID-19. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*. 23. 10.1177/14657503211046849.
- M. Matarazzo, L. Penco, G. Profumo, R. Quaglia (2021). Digital transformation and customer value creation in Made in Italy SMEs: A dynamic capabilities perspective. *Journal of Business Research*, 123 (2021), pp. 642-656, 10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.10.033
- E. Nichifor, R.C. Lixăndroi, S. Sumedrea, I.B. Chițu, G. Brătucu. (2021). How can SMEs become more sustainable? Modelling the M-commerce consumer behaviour with contingent free shipping and customer journey's touchpoints optimisation. *Sustainability*, 13 (12) (2021), p. 6845, 10.3390/su13126845"
- Wallis, T., & Dorey, P. (2023). Implementing Partnerships in Energy Supply Chain Cybersecurity Resilience. *Energies*, 16(4), 1868.
- Castillo, J., Barba, K., & Chen, Q. (2022). ChainSCAN: A Blockchain-Based Supply Chain Alerting Framework for Food Safety. In *International Conference on Science of Cyber Security* (pp. 3-20). Cham: Springer International Publishing."
- Ke Rong. Research agenda for the digital economy (2022). *Journal of Digital Economy*, Volume 1, Issue 1, 2022, Pages 20-31, ISSN 2773-0670, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdec.2022.08.004>.
- Urciuoli, L. (2018). The risk of standards proliferation—An analysis of differences between private and public transport standards. *Transportation research part A: policy and practice*, 116, 591-602."
- Buchicchio, E., Grilli, L., Capobianco, E., Cipriano, S., & Antonini, D. (2022). Invisible supply chain attacks based on trojan source. *Computer*, 55(10), 18-25.
- Garvey, M. D., Samuel, J., & Kretinin, A. (2021). An Ontology of Supply Chain Cybersecurity. In *Cyber Security And Supply Chain Management: Risks, Challenges, And Solutions* (pp. 71-132).
- Siciliano, G. G., & Gaudenzi, B. (2018). The role of supply chain resilience on IT and cyber disruptions. In *Network, Smart and Open: Three Keywords for Information Systems Innovation* (pp. 57-69). Cham: Springer International Publishing."
- "Hsu, C. H., Li, M. G., Zhang, T. Y., Chang, A. Y., Shangguan, S. Z., & Liu, W. L. (2022). Deploying big data enablers to strengthen supply chain resilience to mitigate sustainable risks based on integrated HOQ-MCDM framework. *Mathematics*, 10(8), 1233.

- Colicchia, C., Creazza, A., & Menachof, D. A. (2019). Managing cyber and information risks in supply chains: insights from an exploratory analysis. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 24(2), 215-240."
- "Princes, Elfindah. (2020). Facing Disruptive Challenges in Supply Chain 4.0. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*. 9. 52-57.
- Kopanaki, E. (2022). Conceptualizing supply chain resilience: The role of complex IT infrastructures. *Systems*, 10(2), 35."
- Marinko Skare, María de las Mercedes de Obesso, Samuel Ribeiro-Navarrete. Digital transformation and European small and medium enterprises (SMEs): A comparative study using digital economy and society index data. *International Journal of Information Management*, Volume 68, 2023, 102594. ISSN 0268-4012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2022.102594>.
- "Li, L., Wang, Z., & Zhao, X. (2022). Configurations of financing instruments for supply chain cost reduction: evidence from Chinese manufacturing companies. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 42(9), 1384-1406.
- Hertzel, M., Peng, J., Wu, J., & Zhang, Y. (2018). Global supply chains and cross-border financing. *Production and Operations Management*.
- Urciuoli, L., Gurbuz, M. C., & Val, S. (2018). Choosing Cross-Border Financial Guarantee Instruments—Economic Implications and Hidden Risks. In *Finance and Risk Management for International Logistics and the Supply Chain* (pp. 243-267). Elsevier.
- Jia, F., Blome, C., Sun, H., Yang, Y., & Zhi, B. (2020). Towards an integrated conceptual framework of supply chain finance: An information processing perspective. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 219, 18-30."
- "Akhmedova, Anna & Vila-Brunet, Neus & Mas-Machuca, Marta. (2021). Building trust in sharing economy platforms: trust antecedents and their configurations. *Internet Research*. ahead-of-print. 10.1108/INTR-04-2020-0212.
- Yang, S. B., Lee, K., Lee, H., and Koo, C. (2019), In Airbnb we trust: understanding consumers' trust-attachment building mechanisms in the sharing economy", *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Vol. 83, pp. 198–209. doi: 10.1016/j.ijhm.2018.10.016.
- J. Andrew Petersen, Brianna JeeWon Paulich, Farnoosh Khodakarami, Stavroula Spyropoulou, V. Kumar. (2022). Customer-based execution strategy in a global digital economy. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, Volume 39, Issue 2, 2022, Pages 566-582. ISSN 0167-8116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2021.09.010>.
- Chen P, Kim S. (2023) The impact of digital transformation on innovation performance - The mediating role of innovation factors. *Heliyon*. 2023 Feb 22;9(3):e13916. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13916. PMID: 36895347; PMCID: PMC9988549.
- Amrollahi A, Kummer T, Rajaeian MM. (2022) Trusting Strangers: The Role of Trust in the Acceptance of Sharing Economy Platforms during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Australasian Conference on Information Systems 2022*
- Haowen, F, Yulin Z. (2021). Quality disclosure in sharing economy platform with network externality under consumer risk aversion. *Kybernetes: The International Journal of Systems & Cybernetics*, Volume 52, Number 5, 2021, pp. 1816-1841(26). <https://doi.org/10.1108/K-06-2021-0511>"

- Bogataj, D., Battini, D., Calzavara, M., & Persona, A. (2019). The ageing workforce challenge: Investments in collaborative robots or contribution to pension schemes, from the multi-echelon perspective. *International journal of production economics*, 210, 97-106.
- Battini, D., Berti, N., Finco, S., Zennaro, I., & Das, A. (2022). Towards industry 5.0: A multi-objective job rotation model for an inclusive workforce. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 250, 108619. "
- Cox, V., & Overbey, J. A. (2022). Generational knowledge transfer and retention strategies. *Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal*, (ahead-of-print).
- Serenko, A. (2022). The great resignation: the great knowledge exodus or the onset of the great knowledge revolution?. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, (ahead-of-print)."
- Li, L. (2022). Reskilling and upskilling the future-ready workforce for industry 4.0 and beyond. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 1-16.
- Doherty, O., & Stephens, S. (2021). The skill needs of the manufacturing industry: can higher education keep up?. *Education+ Training*, 63(4), 632-646.
- Mourtzis, D., Panopoulos, N., & Angelopoulos, J. (2022). A hybrid teaching factory model towards personalized education 4.0. *International Journal of Computer Integrated Manufacturing*, 1-21."
- Christ, K. L., & Helliard, C. V. (2021). Blockchain technology and modern slavery: Reducing deceptive recruitment in migrant worker populations. *Journal of Business Research*, 131, 112-120.
- Benstead, A. V., Mwesumbe, D., Moradlou, H., & Boffelli, A. (2022). Entering the world behind the clothes that we wear: practical applications of blockchain technology. *Production Planning & Control*, 1-18."
- Calzavara, M., Battini, D., Bogataj, D., Sgarbossa, F., & Zennaro, I. (2020). Ageing workforce management in manufacturing systems: state of the art and future research agenda. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(3), 729-747.
- Zhang, M., Grosse, E. H., & Glock, C. H. (2023). Ergonomic and economic evaluation of a collaborative hybrid order picking system. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 258, 108774.
- Sodhi, M. S., & Tang, C. S. (2021). Supply chain management for extreme conditions: research opportunities. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 57(1), 7-16."
- Franke, J., & Gailhofer, P. (2021). Data Governance and Regulation for Sustainable Smart Cities. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, 3, 763788.
- Simoni, M. D., Kutanoğlu, E., & Claudel, C. G. (2020). Optimization and analysis of a robot-assisted last mile delivery system. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 142, 102049.
- Mohamed, N., Al-Jaroodi, J., Jawhar, I., Idries, A., & Mohammed, F. (2020). Unmanned aerial vehicles applications in future smart cities. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 153, 119293.
- Pan, S., Zhou, W., Piramuthu, S., Giannikas, V., & Chen, C. (2021). Smart city for sustainable urban freight logistics. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(7), 2079-2089.

- Nagarajan, S. M., Deverajan, G. G., Chatterjee, P., Alnumay, W., & Muthukumaran, V. (2022). Integration of IoT based routing process for food supply chain management in sustainable smart cities. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 76, 103448."
- Haque, A. B., Bhushan, B., & Dhiman, G. (2022). Conceptualizing smart city applications: Requirements, architecture, security issues, and emerging trends. *Expert Systems*, 39(5), e12753.
- Pedersen, S. H., & Picot, G. (2023). Regulating low wages: cross-national policy variation and outcomes. *Socio-Economic Review*, mwad019.
- Wotschack, P. (2020). Drivers of training participation in low skilled jobs: the role of 'voice', technology, innovation and labor shortages in German companies. *International Journal of Training and Development*, 24(3), 245-264.
- Haque, A. B., Bhushan, B., & Dhiman, G. (2022). Conceptualizing smart city applications: Requirements, architecture, security issues, and emerging trends. *Expert Systems*, 39(5), e12753.
- Kolade, O., & Owoseni, A. (2022). Employment 5.0: The work of the future and the future of work. *Technology in Society*, 102086.."
- Friedland, J., & Balkin, D. B. (2023). When gig workers become essential: Leveraging customer moral self-awareness beyond COVID-19. *Business Horizons*, 66(2), 181-190.
- Mukherjee, AA., Raj, A., & Aggarwal, S. (2023). Identification of barriers and their mitigation strategies for industry 5.0 implementation in emerging economies. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 257, 108770. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2023.108770>."
- Mohamed, N., Al-Jaroodi, J., Jawhar, I., Idries, A., & Mohammed, F. (2020). Unmanned aerial vehicles applications in future smart cities. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 153, 119293.
- Yu, Z., Song, L., Jiang, L., & Sharafi, O. K. (2021). Systematic literature review on the security challenges of blockchain in IoT-based smart cities. *Kybernetes*, 51(1), 323-347."
- Zidi, S., Hamani, N., & Kermad, L. (2022). New metrics for measuring supply chain reconfigurability. *Journal of intelligent manufacturing*, 33(8), 2371-2392.
- Dolgui, A., Ivanov, D., & Sokolov, B. (2020). Reconfigurable supply chain: The X-network. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(13), 4138-4163.
- Sonar, H., Gunasekaran, A., Agrawal, S., & Roy, M. (2022). Role of lean, agile, resilient, green, and sustainable paradigm in supplier selection. *Cleaner Logistics and Supply Chain*, 4, 100059."
- Montecchi, M., Plangger, K., & West, D. C. (2021). Supply chain transparency: A bibliometric review and research agenda. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 238, 108152.
- Hastig, G. M., & Sodhi, M. S. (2020). Blockchain for supply chain traceability: Business requirements and critical success factors. *Production and Operations Management*, 29(4), 935-954.
- Jensen, S. F., Kristensen, J. H., Adamsen, S., Christensen, A., & Waehrens, B. V. (2023). Digital product passports for a circular economy: Data needs for product life cycle decision-making. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 37, 242-255."
- Abbate, S., Centobelli, P., & Cerchione, R. (2023). From Fast to Slow: An Exploratory Analysis of Circular Business Models in the Italian Apparel Industry. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 260, 108824.

- Chevrollier, N., Argyrou, A., Ainiwaer, N., & Nijhof, A. (2023). On the encroachment of sustainable value propositions: Business model innovation for impact. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 382, 135341."
- Jin, B. E., & Shin, D. C. (2020). Changing the game to compete: Innovations in the fashion retail industry from the disruptive business model. *Business Horizons*, 63(3), 301-311.
- Huang, S., Potter, A., & Eysers, D. (2020). Social media in operations and supply chain management: State-of-the-Art and research directions. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(6), 1893-1925.
- Jiang, Z., Yuan, S., Ma, J., & Wang, Q. (2022). The evolution of production scheduling from Industry 3.0 through Industry 4.0. *International Journal of Production Research*, 60(11), 3534-3554."
- Khan, S. A. R., Zkik, K., Belhadi, A., & Kamble, S. S. (2021). Evaluating barriers and solutions for social sustainability adoption in multi-tier supply chains. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(11), 3378-3397.
- P. Sinha, M. Sharma, and R. Agrawal, "A systematic review and future research agenda for sustainable fashion in the apparel industry," *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, no. ahead-of-print, 2022.
- R. Zanjirani Farahani, N. Asgari, and L. N. Van Wassenhove, "Fast fashion, charities, and the circular economy: challenges for operations management," *Prod Oper Manag*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 1089–1114, 2022.
- Khan, S. A. R., Zkik, K., Belhadi, A., & Kamble, S. S. (2021). Evaluating barriers and solutions for social sustainability adoption in multi-tier supply chains. *International Journal of Production Research*, 59(11), 3378-3397."
- Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., & Esposito, E. (2020). Pursuing supply chain sustainable development goals through the adoption of green practices and enabling technologies: A cross-country analysis of LSPs. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 153, 119920.
- Agyabeng-Mensah, Y., Ahenkorah, E., Afum, E., Agyemang, A. N., Agnikpe, C., & Rogers, F. (2020). Examining the influence of internal green supply chain practices, green human resource management and supply chain environmental cooperation on firm performance. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 25(5), 585-599."
- Saghiri, S., Wilding, R., Mena, C., & Bourlakis, M. (2017). Toward a three-dimensional framework for omni-channel. *Journal of Business Research*, 77, 53-67.
- K. Bohmeyer, "The Impact of New E-Commerce Shopping Behaviors," *Supply Chain Brain*, 2021. <https://www.supplychainbrain.com/blogs/1-think-tank/post/32668-the-impact-of-new-e-commerce-shopping-behaviors>"
- Cai, Y. J., & Lo, C. K. (2020). Omni-channel management in the new retailing era: A systematic review and future research agenda. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 229, 107729.
- Nguyen, T., Li, Z. H. O. U., Spiegler, V., Ieromonachou, P., & Lin, Y. (2018). Big data analytics in supply chain management: A state-of-the-art literature review. *Computers & Operations Research*, 98, 254-264.

Wang, G., Gunasekaran, A., Ngai, E. W., & Papadopoulos, T. (2016). Big data analytics in logistics and supply chain management: Certain investigations for research and applications. *International journal of production economics*, 176, 98-110."

M. Hooper, Kate; Benton, "The Future of Remote Work," 2022. [Online]. Available: https://www.migrationpolicy.org/sites/default/files/publications/mpi-remote-work-2022_final.pdf

Chae, B. K., McHaney, R., & Sheu, C. (2020). Exploring social media use in B2B supply chain operations. *Business Horizons*, 63(1), 73-84.

Al Mashalah, H., Hassini, E., Gunasekaran, A., & Bhatt, D. (2022). The impact of digital transformation on supply chains through e-commerce: Literature review and a conceptual framework. *Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review*, 165, 102837.

u, C. W., Dai, K., Ullah, S., & Andlib, Z. (2022). COVID-19 pandemic and unemployment dynamics in European economies. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 35(1), 1752-1764."

Macdonald, J. R., Conroy, S., Eckerd, S., & Becker, W. J. (2023). Where are the workers? Leadership-follower fit and behavioral work withdrawal in the logistics supply chain. *Journal of Business Logistics*.

Thomas, S. P., Liao-Troth, S., & Williams, D. F. (2020). Inefficacy: the tipping point of driver burnout. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 50(4), 483-501."

Macdonald, J. R., Conroy, S., Eckerd, S., & Becker, W. J. (2023). Where are the workers? Leadership-follower fit and behavioral work withdrawal in the logistics supply chain. *Journal of Business Logistics*.

Thomas, S. P., Liao-Troth, S., & Williams, D. F. (2020). Inefficacy: the tipping point of driver burnout. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 50(4), 483-501."

Schroth, H. (2019). Are you ready for Gen Z in the workplace?. *California Management Review*, 61(3), 5-18.

Janssen, D., & Carradini, S. (2021). Generation Z workplace communication habits and expectations. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication*, 64(2), 137-153."

Schroth, H. (2019). Are you ready for Gen Z in the workplace?. *California Management Review*, 61(3), 5-18.

Janssen, D., & Carradini, S. (2021). Generation Z workplace communication habits and expectations. *IEEE Transactions on Professional Communication*, 64(2), 137-153."

Smink, A. R., Frowijn, S., van Reijmersdal, E. A., van Noort, G., & Neijens, P. C. (2019). Try online before you buy: How does shopping with augmented reality affect brand responses and personal data disclosure. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 35, 100854.

Escursell, S., Llorach-Massana, P., & Roncero, M. B. (2021). Sustainability in e-commerce packaging: A review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 280, 124314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124314>

Cullinane, S. (2009). From bricks to clicks: the impact of online retailing on transport and the environment. *Transport Reviews*, 29(6), 759-776.

Buldeo Rai, H., Verlinde, S., & Macharis, C. (2019). The "next day, free delivery" myth unravelled: Possibilities for sustainable last mile transport in an omnichannel environment. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 47(1), 39-54."

Smink, A. R., Frowijn, S., van Reijmersdal, E. A., van Noort, G., & Neijens, P. C. (2019). Try online before you buy: How does shopping with augmented reality affect brand responses and personal data disclosure. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 35, 100854.

Escursell, S., Llorach-Massana, P., & Roncero, M. B. (2021). Sustainability in e-commerce packaging: A review. *Journal of cleaner production*, 280, 124314.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124314>

Cullinane, S. (2009). From bricks to clicks: the impact of online retailing on transport and the environment. *Transport Reviews*, 29(6), 759-776.

Buldeo Rai, H., Verlinde, S., & Macharis, C. (2019). The "next day, free delivery" myth unravelled: Possibilities for sustainable last mile transport in an omnichannel environment. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 47(1), 39-54."

Maloni, M. J., Gligor, D. M., Cheramie, R. A., & Boyd, E. M. (2019). Supervisor and mentoring effects on work-family conflict in logistics. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 49(6), 644-661.

Goffnett, S. P., Cook, R. L., Williams, Z., & Gibson, B. J. (2012). Understanding satisfaction with supply chain management careers: an exploratory study. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 23(1), 135-158.

Rowell, R. (2023). How has geopolitics changed the skills needed by supply chain execs?, available at: <https://www.cips.org/supply-management/news/2023/january/how-has-geopolitics-changed-the-skills-needed-by-supply-chain-execs/>

Adecco Group (2022). The Future of Workforce and Talent in the Logistics & Supply Chain Industry. Available at: <https://www.adecco-jobs.com/-/media/project/adeccogroup/pdf-files/2022-october/logistics-whitepaper-tag-2022-final.pdf/>

Merkert, R., & Hoberg, K. (2022). The Future of Logistics and Supply Chain Management: Changing Skill Sets and Smart Career Choices. In *Global Logistics and Supply Chain Strategies for the 2020s: Vital Skills for the Next Generation* (pp. 1-27). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

Srivastava, S., & Dubey, R. (2014). Supply chain skill gap modelling using interpretive structural modelling and MICMAC analysis. *International Journal of Operations and Quantitative Management*, 20(1), 33-47."

Accenture. (2021) Where's your supply chain workforce headed? Available at: <https://www.accenture.com/content/dam/accenture/final/a-com-migration/manual/r3/pdf/pdf-173/Accenture-Where%27s-Your-Supply-Chain-Workforce-Headed.pdf>

R. Sanders (2021). What enterprises can do to help solve the supply chain talent gap, EY, 2021. https://www.ey.com/en_gr/consulting/what-enterprises-can-do-to-help-solve-the-supply-chain-talent-gap"

S. Knut, Aliche; Hoberg, Kai; Fischer, Julian; Welter (2022). The future of work in supply chain, *Supply Chain Quarterly*, 2022. <https://www.supplychainquarterly.com/articles/6233-the-future-of-work-in-supply-chain>

Accenture. (2021) Where's your supply chain workforce headed? Available at: <https://www.accenture.com/content/dam/accenture/final/a-com-migration/manual/r3/pdf/pdf-173/Accenture-Where%27s-Your-Supply-Chain-Workforce-Headed.pdf>"

Green, A. (2019). Low-skilled employment in a new immigration regime: Challenges and opportunities for business transitions. *National Institute Economic Review*, 248, R17-R27.

1-Haapala, K. R., Zhao, F., Camelio, J., Sutherland, J. W., Skerlos, S. J., Dornfeld, D. A., ... & Rickli, J. L. (2013). A review of engineering research in sustainable manufacturing. *Journal of manufacturing science and engineering*, 135(4), 041013.

K. Fowler. (2021) Five Reasons Labor Shortages Are Impacting Supply Chains. *Forbes*, 2021. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbeshumanresourcescouncil/2021/10/19/five-reasons-labor-shortages-are-impacting-supply-chains/?sh=73b5b4615b94>"

Maintaining and developing skills of a multigenerational workforce," OECD. <https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/sites/b642f807-en/index.html?itemId=/content/component/b642f807-en#chapter-d1e14233>

Accenture. (2021) Where's your supply chain workforce headed? Available at: <https://www.accenture.com/content/dam/accenture/final/a-com-migration/manual/r3/pdf/pdf-173/Accenture-Where%27s-Your-Supply-Chain-Workforce-Headed.pdf>"

Benfeldt, O., Persson, J.S. & Madsen, S. (2020) Data Governance as a Collective Action Problem. *Inf Syst Front* 22, 299–313 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-019-09923-z>.

Michael Sony & Subhash Naik (2020) Critical factors for the successful implementation of Industry 4.0: a review and future research direction, *Production Planning & Control*, 31:10, 799-815, DOI: 10.1080/09537287.2019.1691278"

Matthew D. Jones, Scott Hutcheson, Jorge D. Camba, (2021). Past, present, and future barriers to digital transformation in manufacturing: A review, *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 60, 936-948 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2021.03.006>.

Henderson, J. and Corry, M. (2021), Data literacy training and use for educational professionals, *Journal of Research in Innovative Teaching & Learning*, Vol. 14 No. 2, pp. 232-244. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JRIT-11-2019-0074>

"Ashish Kumar Jha, Maher A.N. Agi, Eric W.T. Ngai (2020). A note on big data analytics capability development in supply chain, *Decision Support Systems*, 138, 113382. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2020.113382>.

Richard Addo-Tenkorang, Petri T. Helo (2016). Big data applications in operations/supply-chain management: A literature review. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 101, 528-543. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2016.09.023>. "

Messina, D., Soares, A.L., Barros, A.C., & Zimmermann, R. (2022) How visible is your supply chain? A model for supply chain visibility assessment. *Supply Chain Forum: An International Journal*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/16258312.2022.2079955>.

Pedro P. Senna, Luís Miguel D.F. Ferreira, Ana C. Barros, Jaime Bonín Roca, Vanessa Magalhães (2022). Prioritizing barriers for the adoption of Industry 4.0 technologies. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 171, 108428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2022.108428>.

Mostafa Al-Emran, Charla Griffy-Brown (2023). The role of technology adoption in sustainable development: Overview, opportunities, challenges, and future research agendas. *Technology in Society*, 73, 102240, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102240>.

- Mukherjee, AA., Raj, A., & Aggarwal, S. (2023). Identification of barriers and their mitigation strategies for industry 5.0 implementation in emerging economies. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 257, 108770. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2023.108770>.
- Fukuda, K., (2020). Science, technology and innovation ecosystem transformation toward society 5.0. *Int. J. Prod. Econ.* 220, 107460. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.07.033>
- Mukherjee, AA., Raj, A., & Aggarwal, S. (2023). Identification of barriers and their mitigation strategies for industry 5.0 implementation in emerging economies. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 257, 108770. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2023.108770>.
- Xu, X., Lu, Y., Vogel-Heuser, B., Wang, L. (2021). Industry 4.0 and industry 5.0—inception, conception and perception. *J. Manuf. Syst.* 61, 530–535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2021.10.006>"
- Dornelles, J.A., Ayala, N.F. & Frank, A.G. (2022). Smart Working in Industry 4.0: How digital technologies enhance manufacturing workers' activities. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 163, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2021.107804>.
- Romero, D. & Stahre, J. (2021). Towards The Resilient Operator 5.0: The Future of Work in Smart Resilient Manufacturing Systems. *Procedia CIRP*, 104, 1089-1094, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2021.11.183>."
- Ivanov., D. (2023). The Industry 5.0 framework: viability-based integration of the resilience, sustainability, and human-centricity perspectives. *International Journal of Production Research*, 61(5), 1683-1695. [10.1080/00207543.2022.2118892](https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2022.2118892)
- Panetto, H., lung, B., Ivanov, D., Weichhart, G., & Wang, X. (2019). Challenges for the cyber-physical manufacturing enterprises of the future. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 47, 200-213, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arcontrol.2019.02.002>."
- Althaf, S., Babbitt, C.W. (2021). Disruption risks to material supply chains in the electronics sector. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 167, 105248, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.105248>.
- Shih, W. (2020). Global Supply Chains in a Post-Pandemic World. *Harvard Business Review*, (September–October 2020. <http://ringmar.net/mycourses/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Shih-2020-Global-Supply-Chains-in-a-Post-Pandemic-World.pdf>"
- Cole, C., Gnanapragasam, A., Cooper, T., & Singh, J. (2019). Assessing barriers to reuse of electrical and electronic equipment, a UK perspective. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*: X, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100004>
- Potting, J., Hekkert, M.P., Worrell, E., Hanemaaijer, A. (2017). *Circular Economy: Measuring Innovation in the Product Chain*. Policy Report. PBL Publishers.
- Sonogo, M., Echeveste, M. E. S., & Debarba, H. G. (2022). Repair of electronic products: Consumer practices and institutional initiatives. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 30, 556–565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.12.031> "
- "Benfeldt, O., Persson, J.S. & Madsen, S. Data Governance as a Collective Action Problem. *Inf Syst Front* 22, 299–313 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-019-09923-z>.
- Michael Sony & Subhash Naik (2020) Critical factors for the successful implementation of Industry 4.0: a review and future research direction, *Production Planning & Control*, 31:10, 799-815, DOI: [10.1080/09537287.2019.1691278](https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2019.1691278)"

- Raj, A., Dwivedi, G., Sharma, A., Jabbour, A.B.L.S., & Rajak, S. (2020). Barriers to the adoption of industry 4.0 technologies in the manufacturing sector: An inter-country comparative perspective. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 224, 107546, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.107546>.
- Dalzochio, J., Kunst, R., Pignaton, E., Binotto, A., Sanyal, A., Favilla, J., & Barbosa, J. (2020). Machine learning and reasoning for predictive maintenance in Industry 4.0: Current status and challenges. *Computers in Industry*, 123, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2020.103298>.
- Alani, M.M., Alloghani, M. (2019). Security Challenges in the Industry 4.0 Era. In: Dastbaz, M., Cochrane, P. (eds) *Industry 4.0 and Engineering for a Sustainable Future*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-12953-8_8
- Benfeldt, O., Persson, J.S. & Madsen, S. Data Governance as a Collective Action Problem. *Inf Syst Front* 22, 299–313 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10796-019-09923-z>.
- Michael Sony & Subhash Naik (2020) Critical factors for the successful implementation of Industry 4.0: a review and future research direction, *Production Planning & Control*, 31:10, 799-815, DOI: 10.1080/09537287.2019.1691278"
- Matthew D. Jones, Scott Hutcheson, Jorge D. Camba, (2021). Past, present, and future barriers to digital transformation in manufacturing: A review, *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 60, 936-948 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2021.03.006>.
- Elavarasan, R.M., Afridhis, S., Vijayaraghavan, R.R., Subramaniam, U., & Nurunnabi, M. (2020). SWOT analysis: A framework for comprehensive evaluation of drivers and barriers for renewable energy development in significant countries. *Energy Reports*, 6, 1838-1864, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2020.07.007>
- Seetharaman, Moorthy, K., Patwa, N., Saravanan, Yash Gupta (2019). Breaking barriers in deployment of renewable energy. *Heliyon*, 5(1), e01166, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e01166>."
- Herbes, C., Rilling, B., & Holstenkamp, L. (2021). Ready for new business models? Human and social capital in the management of renewable energy cooperatives in Germany. *Energy Policy*, 156, 112417, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2021.112417>.
- Sweeney, C., Bessa, R.J., Browell, J., & Pinson, P. (2019). The future of forecasting for renewable energy. *WIREs Energy and environment*, 9(2), e365, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.365>"
- Cole, C., Gnanapragasam, A., Cooper, T., & Singh, J. (2019). Assessing barriers to reuse of electrical and electronic equipment, a UK perspective. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling: X*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100004>
- Potting, J., Hekkert, M.P., Worrell, E., Hanemaaijer, A. (2017). *Circular Economy: Measuring Innovation in the Product Chain*. Policy Report. PBL Publishers.
- Sonogo, M., Echeveste, M. E. S., & Debarba, H. G. (2022). Repair of electronic products: Consumer practices and institutional initiatives. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 30, 556–565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.12.031> "
- Cole, C., Gnanapragasam, A., Cooper, T., & Singh, J. (2019). Assessing barriers to reuse of electrical and electronic equipment, a UK perspective. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling: X*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100004>

- Potting, J., Hekkert, M.P., Worrell, E., Hanemaaijer, A. (2017). Circular Economy: Measuring Innovation in the Product Chain. Policy Report. PBL Publishers.
- Sonego, M., Echeveste, M. E. S., & Debarba, H. G. (2022). Repair of electronic products: Consumer practices and institutional initiatives. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 30, 556–565. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.12.032>
- "Deloitte (2019). Understanding the regulatory requirements of the MAS Payment Service Act <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0925527321003716?via%3Dihub>
- Wu. Jiangong, Jiang. Nan, Wu. Zhelun, Jiang. Hongyan (2021). Early warning of risks in cross-border mobile payments
- Zippel, C., & Bohnet-Joschko, S. (2017). Post market surveillance in the german medical device sector—current state and future perspectives. *Health Policy*, 121(8), 880-886.
- Ramachandran. G. S., Deane. F., Malil. S., Dorri. A., Jurdak. R. (2021): Towards Assisted Autonomy for Supply Chain Compliance Management
- Sun. Wenchuan, Xiamen. P. R. (2022). Application of the Blockchain Technology in the Supply Chain Finance
- Committee on Payments and Market Infrastructures Improving access to payment systems for cross-border payments: best practices for self-assessments," (2022), Accessed: May 15, 2023. [Online]. Available: www.bis.org 10.1111/ijcs.12733
- McKinsey (2020). The consumer-data opportunity and the privacy imperative
- Gilad, S. (2010). It runs in the family: Meta-regulation and its siblings. *Regulation & Governance*, 4(4), 485-506.
- Blind, K., Petersen, S. S., & Riillo, C. A. (2017). The impact of standards and regulation on innovation in uncertain markets. *Research policy*, 46(1), 249-264.
- Aspray. William, Doty. Philip (2023). Does technology really outpace policy, and does it matter? A primer for technical experts and others"
- Gal, M. S., & Aviv, O. (2020). The competitive effects of the GDPR. *Journal of Competition Law & Economics*, 16(3), 349-391.
- Roca, J. B., & O'Sullivan, E. (2022). The role of regulators in mitigating uncertainty within the Valley of Death. *Technovation*, 109, 102157.
- Adrian. F., Ameer. A., Seyed Aku. G., Julia. D. (2023): The impact of GDPR infringement fines on the market value of firms
- Zhang, T., Qin, H. & Xu, W. (2022). Environmental Regulation, Greenwashing Behavior, and Green Governance of High-Pollution Enterprises in China
- Tambe. Pratap, Tambay. Purna (2020). Reducing Modern Slavery Using AI and Blockchain
- Liudmyla. Strikha, Ella. Mamontoava, Sergiy. Vonsovykh, Tatiana. Voropayeva, Zorinana. Buryk, Olena. Baranova (2021). The modern experience of lobbying interests in Europe
- Cho, S. H., Fang, X., Tayur, S., & Xu, Y. (2019). Combating child labor: Incentives and information disclosure in global supply chains. *Manufacturing & Service Operations Management*, 21(3), 692-711. https://lieferkettengesetz.de/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/Initiative-Lieferkettengesetz_FAQ-English.pdf

- Kirkman, R., & Voulvoulis, N. (2017). The role of public communication in decision making for waste management infrastructure. *Journal of environmental management*, 203, 640-647. Tsia. Feng Ming, Bui. Tat-Dat et al. (2020). A performance assessment approach for integrated solid waste management using a sustainable balanced scorecard approach
- Dan. Dobrota, Gabriela. Dobrota, Tiberiu. Dobrescu (2020). Improvement of waste tyre recycling technology based on a new tyre markings
- Soundararajan, V., Wilhelm, M. M., & Crane, A. (2021). Humanizing research on working conditions in Supply chains: Building a path to decent work. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 57(2), 3-13.
- Keller, J., Jung, M., & Lasch, R. (2022). Sustainability Governance: Insights from a Cocoa Supply Chain. *Sustainability*, 14(17), 10763.
- Dasgupta, S., & Robinson, E. J. (2023). The labour force in a changing climate: Research and policy needs. *PLOS Climate*, 2(1), e0000131."
- "Gärtner, L., & Schoen, H. (2021). Experiencing climate change: revisiting the role of local weather in affecting climate change awareness and related policy preferences. *Climatic Change*, 167(3-4), 31.
- Yu, T. Y., Parsons, D., Nakakita, E., Tsuda, T., & Ishikawa, H. (2015). Mitigating the impact of severe weather and climate variability through innovative sensing, modeling, and prediction. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 96(1), ES13-ES16.
- Wang, F., Harindintwali, J. D., Wei, K., Shan, Y., Mi, Z., Costello, M. J., ... & Tiedje, J. M. (2023). Climate change: Strategies for mitigation and adaptation. *The Innovation Geoscience*, 1(1), 100015-1."
- Winkler, J. A., Soldo, L., Tang, Y., Forbush, T., Douches, D. S., Long, C. M., ... & Buell, C. R. (2018). Potential impacts of climate change on storage conditions for commercial agriculture: an example for potato production in Michigan. *Climatic Change*, 151, 275-287.
- Lesinger, K., Tian, D., Leisner, C. P., & Sanz-Saez, A. (2020). Impact of climate change on storage conditions for major agricultural commodities across the contiguous United States. *Climatic Change*, 162, 1287-1305."
- Melo, S., Macedo, J., & Baptista, P. (2019). Capacity-sharing in logistics solutions: A new pathway towards sustainability. *Transport Policy*, 73, 143-151.
- Gärtner, L., & Schoen, H. (2021). Experiencing climate change: revisiting the role of local weather in affecting climate change awareness and related policy preferences. *Climatic Change*, 167(3-4), 31.
- Yu, T. Y., Parsons, D., Nakakita, E., Tsuda, T., & Ishikawa, H. (2015). Mitigating the impact of severe weather and climate variability through innovative sensing, modeling, and prediction. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 96(1), ES13-ES16."
- Dasgupta, S., & Robinson, E. J. (2023). The labour force in a changing climate: Research and policy needs. *PLOS Climate*, 2(1), e0000131.
- Al-Balushi, Z., & Durugbo, C. M. (2020). Management strategies for supply risk dependencies: empirical evidence from the gulf region. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 50(4), 457-481.

- Golmohammadi, A., & Hassini, E. (2020). Review of supplier diversification and pricing strategies under random supply and demand. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(11), 3455-3487."
- Rong, K., Hu, J., Ma, Y., Lim, M. K., Liu, Y., & Lu, C. (2018). The sharing economy and its implications for sustainable value chains. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 130, 188-189.
- Golmohammadi, A., & Hassini, E. (2020). Review of supplier diversification and pricing strategies under random supply and demand. *International Journal of Production Research*, 58(11), 3455-3487.
- Sunny, J., Undralla, N., & Pillai, V. M. (2020). Supply chain transparency through blockchain-based traceability: An overview with demonstration. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 150, 106895.
- Bingzhang, L., & Zirianov, V. (2021). Blockchain in agricultural supply chain management. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 273, p. 08029). EDP Sciences.
- Niu, B., Xie, F., Mu, Z., & Ji, P. (2020). Multinational firms' local sourcing strategies considering unreliable supply and environmental sustainability. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 155, 104648.
- Soundararajan, V., Wilhelm, M. M., & Crane, A. (2021). Humanizing research on working conditions in Supply chains: Building a path to decent work. *Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 57(2), 3-13.
- Keller, J., Jung, M., & Lasch, R. (2022). Sustainability Governance: Insights from a Cocoa Supply Chain. *Sustainability*, 14(17), 10763.
- Dasgupta, S., & Robinson, E. J. (2023). The labour force in a changing climate: Research and policy needs. *PLOS Climate*, 2(1), e0000131."
- Marchi, B., & Zanoni, S. (2017). Supply chain management for improved energy efficiency: Review and opportunities. *Energies*, 10(10), 1618.
- Widera, B. (2019). Renewable hydrogen as an energy storage solution. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 116, p. 00097). EDP Sciences.
- Wan, P. K., & Huang, L. (2021). Energy Tracing and Blockchain Technology: A Primary Review. In *International Conference on Intelligent Technologies and Applications* (pp. 223-231). Cham: Springer International Publishing."
- "Kumar, A., Bairwa, R. C., Jain, R., Mishra, Y., & Meena, M. L. (2023). A Bibliometric Analysis on Smart Farming Techniques. In *Emerging Trends in Mechanical and Industrial Engineering: Select Proceedings of ICETMIE 2022* (pp. 811-825). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Pradhan, P., Kriewald, S., Costa, L., Rybski, D., Benton, T. G., Fischer, G., & Kropp, J. P. (2020). Urban food systems: how regionalization can contribute to climate change mitigation. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 54(17), 10551-10560.
- Chakraborty, A., Das, S., & Mondal, B. (2022). Integrating Neural Network for Pest Detection in Controlled Environment Vertical Farm. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 15(17), 829-838.
- Gorjian, S., Ebadi, H., Jathar, L. D., & Savoldi, L. (2022). Solar energy for sustainable food and agriculture: developments, barriers, and policies. In *Solar energy advancements in agriculture and food production systems* (pp. 1-28). Academic Press."

APPENDIX 1 – LIST OF PAPERS ON SUPPLY CHAIN SUSTAINABILITY AND RESILIENCE

Authors	Title	Year	Journal
Patidar A., Sharma M., Agrawal R., Sangwan K.S.	Supply chain resilience and its key performance indicators: an evaluation under Industry 4.0 and sustainability perspective	2023	Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal
Silva A.C., Marques C.M., de Sousa J.P.	A Simulation Approach for the Design of More Sustainable and Resilient Supply Chains in the Pharmaceutical Industry	2023	Sustainability (Switzerland)
Singh G., Rajesh R., Daultani Y., Misra S.C.	Resilience and sustainability enhancements in food supply chains using Digital Twin technology: A grey causal modelling (GCM) approach	2023	Computers and Industrial Engineering
Cui L., Jin Z., Li Y., Wang Y.	Effects of control mechanisms on supply chain resilience and sustainability performance	2023	Australian Journal of Management
Singh J., Hamid A.B.A., Garza-Reyes J.A.	Supply chain resilience strategies and their impact on sustainability: an investigation from the automobile sector	2023	Supply Chain Management
Gani M.O., Yoshi T., Rahman M.S.	Optimizing firm's supply chain resilience in data-driven business environment	2023	Journal of Global Operations and Strategic Sourcing
Michel-Villarreal R.	Towards sustainable and resilient short food supply chains: a focus on sustainability practices and resilience capabilities using case study	2023	British Food Journal
Eggert J., Hartmann J.	Sustainable supply chain management – a key to resilience in the global pandemic	2023	Supply Chain Management
Vergara J.I.T., Martínez J.A.S., Salais-Fierro T.E.	Performance measurement of a Resilient-Sustainable Supply Chain through fuzzy multi-criteria techniques	2023	Computers and Industrial Engineering
Di Paola N., Cosimato S., Vona R.	Be resilient today to be sustainable tomorrow: Different perspectives in global supply chains	2023	Journal of Cleaner Production
Silva M.E., Pereira M.M.O., Hendry L.C.	Embracing change in tandem: resilience and sustainability together transforming supply chains	2023	International Journal of Operations and Production Management
Torres Vergara J.I., Saucedo Martínez J.A., Olivo Lucio D.	Resilient and sustainable supply chain criteria for performance evaluation: selection and ranking through fuzzy Delphi	2023	Benchmarking
Shan H., Bai D., Fan X., Shi J., Li Y., Yang S.	Enabling roles of integration and resilience for sustainable supply Chain performance: an empirical study on China's E-commerce platforms	2023	Applied Economics
Pu G., Li S., Bai J.	Effect of supply chain resilience on firm's sustainable competitive advantage: a dynamic capability perspective	2023	Environmental Science and Pollution Research
El Korchi A.	Survivability, resilience and sustainability of supply chains: The COVID-19 pandemic	2022	Journal of Cleaner Production
Silva M.E., Ruel S.	Inclusive purchasing and supply chain resilience capabilities: Lessons for social sustainability	2022	Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management
Zhu X., Wu Y.J.	How Does Supply Chain Resilience Affect Supply Chain Performance? The Mediating Effect of Sustainability	2022	Sustainability (Switzerland)
Kazancoglu I., Ozbiltekin-Pala M., Kumar Mangla S., Kazancoglu Y., Jabeen F.	Role of flexibility, agility and responsiveness for sustainable supply chain resilience during COVID-19	2022	Journal of Cleaner Production

Authors	Title	Year	Journal
Sauer P.C., Silva M.E., Schleper M.C.	Supply chains' sustainability trajectories and resilience: a learning perspective in turbulent environments	2022	International Journal of Operations and Production Management
Salehi S., Zare Mehrjerdi Y., Sadegheih A., Hosseini-Nasab H.	Designing a resilient and sustainable biomass supply chain network through the optimization approach under uncertainty and the disruption	2022	Journal of Cleaner Production
Costa F.H.D.O., de Moraes C.C., da Silva A.L., Delai I., Chaudhuri A., Pereira C.R.	Does resilience reduce food waste? Analysis of Brazilian supplier-retailer dyad	2022	Journal of Cleaner Production
Negri M., Cagno E., Colicchia C.	Building sustainable and resilient supply chains: a framework and empirical evidence on trade-offs and synergies in implementation of practices	2022	Production Planning and Control
Vali-Siar M.M., Roghanian E.	Sustainable, resilient and responsive mixed supply chain network design under hybrid uncertainty with considering COVID-19 pandemic disruption	2022	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Cotta D., Klink L., Alten T., Al Madhoun B.	How do supply chain managers perceive the relationship between resilience and sustainability practices? An exploratory study	2022	Business Strategy and the Environment
Yang Z., Guo X., Sun J., Zhang Y., Wang Y.	What Does Not Kill You Makes You Stronger: Supply Chain Resilience and Corporate Sustainability Through Emerging IT Capability	2022	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management
Negri M., Cagno E., Colicchia C., Sarkis J.	Integrating sustainability and resilience in the supply chain: A systematic literature review and a research agenda	2021	Business Strategy and the Environment
Sazvar Z., Tafakkori K., Oladzad N., Nayeri S.	A capacity planning approach for sustainable-resilient supply chain network design under uncertainty: A case study of vaccine supply chain	2021	Computers and Industrial Engineering
Rajesh R.	Optimal trade-offs in decision-making for sustainability and resilience in manufacturing supply chains	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Mehrjerdi Y.Z., Shafiee M.	A resilient and sustainable closed-loop supply chain using multiple sourcing and information sharing strategies	2021	Journal of Cleaner Production
Ji L., Yuan C., Feng T., Wang C.	Achieving the environmental profits of green supplier integration: The roles of supply chain resilience and knowledge combination	2020	Sustainable Development
Mohammed A.	Towards 'gresilient' supply chain management: A quantitative study	2020	Resources, Conservation and Recycling
Shashi, Centobelli P., Cerchione R., Ertz M.	Managing supply chain resilience to pursue business and environmental strategies	2020	Business Strategy and the Environment
Kaur H., Singh S.P.	Sustainable procurement and logistics for disaster resilient supply chain	2019	Annals of Operations Research
Rajesh R.	Social and environmental risk management in resilient supply chains: A periodical study by the Grey-Verhulst model	2019	International Journal of Production Research
Bag S., Gupta S., Foropon C.	Examining the role of dynamic remanufacturing capability on supply chain resilience in circular economy	2019	Management Decision
Shin N., Park S.	Evidence-based resilience management for supply chain sustainability: An interpretive structural modelling approach	2019	Sustainability (Switzerland)

Authors	Title	Year	Journal
De Souza V., Bloemhof-Ruwaard J., Borsato M.	Exploring ecosystem network analysis to balance resilience and performance in sustainable supply chain design	2019	International Journal of Advanced Operations Management
Ramezankhani M.J., Torabi S.A., Vahidi F.	Supply chain performance measurement and evaluation: A mixed sustainability and resilience approach	2018	Computers and Industrial Engineering
Fahimnia B., Jabbarzadeh A., Sarkis J.	Greening versus resilience: A supply chain design perspective	2018	Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review
Jabbarzadeh A., Fahimnia B., Sabouhi F.	Resilient and sustainable supply chain design: sustainability analysis under disruption risks	2018	International Journal of Production Research
Rajesh R.	On sustainability, resilience, and the sustainable-resilient supply networks	2018	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Ivanov D.	Revealing interfaces of supply chain resilience and sustainability: a simulation study	2018	International Journal of Production Research
Singh R.K., Gupta A., Gunasekaran A.	Analysing the interaction of factors for resilient humanitarian supply chain	2018	International Journal of Production Research
Zahiri B., Zhuang J., Mohammadi M.	Toward an integrated sustainable-resilient supply chain: A pharmaceutical case study	2017	Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review
Fahimnia B., Jabbarzadeh A.	Marrying supply chain sustainability and resilience: A match made in heaven	2016	Transportation Research Part E: Logistics and Transportation Review
Eltantawy R.	Towards sustainable supply management: Requisite governance and resilience capabilities	2015	Journal of Strategic Marketing
Moadab A., Kordi G., Paydar M.M., Divsalar A., Hajiaghahi-Keshteli M.	Designing a sustainable-resilient-responsive supply chain network considering uncertainty in the COVID-19 era	2023	Expert Systems with Applications
Mahmud P., Ahmed M., Janan F., Xames M.D., Chowdhury N.R.	Strategies to develop a sustainable and resilient vaccine supply chain in the context of a developing economy	2023	Socio-Economic Planning Sciences
Mohammed A., Zubairu N., Yazdani M., Diabat A., Li X.	Resilient supply chain network design without lagging sustainability responsibilities	2023	Applied Soft Computing
Attia E.-A., Alarjani A., Uddin M.S., Kineber A.F.	Determining the Stationary Enablers of Resilient and Sustainable Supply Chains	2023	Sustainability (Switzerland)
Khezeli M., Najafi E., Molana M.H., Seidi M.	A sustainable and resilient supply chain (RS-SCM) by using synchronisation and load-sharing approach: application in the oil and gas refinery	2023	International Journal of Systems Science: Operations and Logistics
Ghufuran M., Khan K.I.A., Ullah F., Alaloul W.S., Musarat M.A.	Key Enablers of Resilient and Sustainable Construction Supply Chains: A Systems Thinking Approach	2022	Sustainability (Switzerland)
Hervani A.A., Nandi S., Helms M.M., Sarkis J.	A performance measurement framework for socially sustainable and resilient supply chains using environmental goods valuation methods	2022	Sustainable Production and Consumption
Bechtsis D., Tsolakis N., Iakovou E., Vlachos D.	Data-driven secure, resilient and sustainable supply chains: gaps, opportunities, and a new generalised data sharing and data monetisation framework	2022	International Journal of Production Research
Shafiee M., Zare Mehrjerdi Y., Keshavarz M.	Integrating lean, resilient, and sustainable practices in supply chain network: mathematical modelling and the AUGMECON2 approach	2022	International Journal of Systems Science: Operations and Logistics
Sundarakani B., Pereira V., Ishizaka A.	Robust facility location decisions for resilient sustainable supply chain performance in the face of disruptions	2020	International Journal of Logistics Management
Mousavi Ahranjani P., Ghaderi S.F., Azadeh A., Babazadeh R.	Robust design of a sustainable and resilient bioethanol supply chain under operational and disruption risks	2020	Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy

Authors	Title	Year	Journal
Sen D.K., Datta S., Mahapatra S.S.	On evaluation of supply chain's ecosilient (g-resilient) performance index: A fuzzy embedded decision support framework	2018	Benchmarking
Mari S.I., Lee Y.H., Memon M.S.	Sustainable and resilient supply chain network design under disruption risks	2014	Sustainability (Switzerland)